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38

39 **Introduction**

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41 As most emerging neurons are born away from the location at which they will later function, they often
42 travel long distances before establishing functional neuronal circuits. During this journey, neurons must
43 interpret spatial, chemical and mechanical cues to reach their correct positions¹⁻³. When these cues are
44 misread or disrupted, neurons can become misdirected to ectopic positions which often leads to severe
45 brain developmental defects⁴⁻⁶. Emerging neurons using radial and tangential migration modes like
46 cortical excitatory neurons and inhibitory interneurons, respectively, have been extensively studied,
47 particularly in the rodent neocortex. There, studies have uncovered the diverse intracellular,
48 intercellular, and extracellular matrix (ECM)-related mechanisms as well as classical axon guidance
49 molecules, that together orchestrate the stereotypic migration and polarization of these cells leading to
50 cortical layering also known as neuronal lamination^{2,7-9}.

51 However, both inter- and projection neurons also move via multipolar migration, characterized by
52 frequent directional changes and multiple dynamic protrusions¹⁰⁻¹². A main difference between neurons
53 undergoing radial- or tangential migration and neurons undergoing multipolar migration, is that
54 multipolar migrating neurons lack stable attachments. While this most likely makes multipolar
55 migration more flexible, it is currently not fully understood how multipolar migrating cells navigate
56 through the crowded brain tissue and find their exact functional positions despite the lack of direct
57 physical attachments of other physical cues.

58 Neurons undergoing multipolar migration are prevalent across brain regions, including the cortex,
59 hippocampus as well as the retina. In addition, this migration mode is conserved across vertebrates, and
60 can be found in fish, reptiles, chick, rodents and ferrets¹⁰⁻¹⁷. In reptiles and chick, multipolar migration
61 is actually the dominant mode of migration responsible for cortical layering¹⁸. Despite this prevalence,
62 the mechanisms that guide multipolar migration are much less explored than radial and tangential
63 migration modes. This lack of understanding most likely results from the fact that neuronal migration
64 has been largely studied in organotypic slice culture of non-transparent rodent brains¹⁹, where
65 multipolar migration is less common.

66 To uncover the guiding principles that steer multipolar migration, we here investigate the migration of
67 retinal interneurons, horizontal cells (HC), in the transparent and accessible zebrafish retina. As an
68 important part of the brain responsible for the reaction to visual stimuli, the retina shows a highly
69 conserved laminar architecture across vertebrates^{20,21}. Out of five neuronal cell types in the developing
70 retina: photoreceptors, bipolar cells, retinal ganglion cells, amacrine cells (AC) and HCs, multipolar
71 migration has been observed for all except bipolar cells. Among these, HCs most prominently exhibit
72 this mode of migration, traveling bidirectionally across the developing inner nuclear layer²²⁻³⁰ (Figures
73 1A, S1A and Video S1). Following this bidirectional migration phase, mature HCs settle beneath the

74 photoreceptor layer to modify the visual signal as an integral component of the conserved retinal
75 functional circuit³¹.

76 In addition to the characteristics of HC multipolar migration, the environmental context in which this
77 occurs is notably distinct from that of other neuronal migration modes. HC migration takes place in an
78 environment without prominent fibrous ECM or notable stiffness gradients³², meaning that these cells
79 move without anchoring to stable physical substrates. While prior studies have documented the
80 dynamics and morphology of migrating multipolar HCs^{25,32}, how these cells interpret their surrounding
81 environment to find their precise laminar positioning remains unclear. In particular, the factors
82 triggering timely HC departure from the basal AC layer and guiding their non-stereotypic migration
83 towards the photoreceptors are poorly understood.

84 Here, we fill this gap and reveal guidance molecules that steer correct and reproducible HC multipolar
85 migration. By systemically probing the influence of neighboring retinal cell types on HC navigation
86 and combining cell-type-specific transcriptomics using an *in vivo* CRISPR screen, we identify novel
87 ligand–receptor interactions between the moving HCs and their changing environment. Overall, we find
88 that HCs interpret spatially distinct attractive and repulsive cues, potentially through their multiple
89 dynamic protrusions, to integrate directional information as they move. These findings define a
90 molecular framework for multipolar migration in complex environments lacking classical ECM-based
91 or cellular scaffolds and may reflect a generalizable strategy for multipolar migration in the developing
92 brain and beyond.

93

94

95 **Results**

96

97 **Multipolar horizontal cell migration through the crowded inner nuclear layer occurs** 98 **independently of bipolar cells.**

99 When leaving the AC layer, multipolar HCs extend various long processes and take individual paths as
100 they advance through the developing inner nuclear layer to reach their final laminar location below the
101 photoreceptors²⁵. The part of the inner nuclear layer through which HCs move apically, is mainly
102 occupied by bipolar cells at a developmental stage when bipolar cell nuclei are reaching theoretical
103 packing limits^{33,34} (Figure 1C). We thus asked whether and how bipolar cells could influence or guide
104 ECM-independent multipolar HC migration in this crowded tissue environment. To understand if
105 bipolar cells could provide instructive signals or a physical scaffold for HC migration, we depleted
106 bipolar cells by targeting both *Vsx1* and *Vsx2* transcription factors, crucial in determining the bipolar
107 cell fate^{35,36}. We injected pre-assembled Cas9 protein/gRNA ribonucleoprotein complexes (RNPs)
108 targeting three loci in both *vsx1* and *vsx2*, to generate F0 knockout (KO) embryos³⁷ in a *Tg(vsx1:GFP;*
109 *ptf1a:DsRed)* reporter line. This line labels both, possibly remaining bipolar cells (via *vsx1*) and retinal
110 interneurons (HCs and ACs, via *ptf1a*), respectively. In agreement with previous reports showing

111 general robustness of retinal architecture upon depletion of different neuronal cell populations^{38,39}, we
112 observed that in the *vsx1+vsx2* KO scenario, the inner nuclear layer laminated on first sight similar to
113 controls. However, the volume normally occupied by bipolar cells, was taken up by DsRed-positive
114 cells, most likely the ACs (Figure S1B). Next, performing the same knockout in a *Tg(lhx1:GFP);*
115 *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* reporter line labelling both HCs (*lhx1* and *ptf1a*) and ACs (*ptf1a*), we found that HC
116 migration and lamination were largely unaffected by the absence of bipolar cells (Figures 1D, 1F).
117 Further, when conducting in vivo imaging of the developing *vsx1+vsx2* F0 KO retina, we did not
118 observe obvious differences in HCs apical migration dynamics (Video S2). Together, this strongly
119 suggests that whereas bipolar cells are crucial for visual stimuli processing in mature retinae³⁵, they do
120 not appear to provide guidance, nor function as a physical scaffold to migrating multipolar HCs.

121

122 **Photoreceptor cell depletion causes horizontal cells to overshoot to ectopic apical positions.**

123 We showed that in the absence of bipolar cells, migrating HCs still reach their final position beneath
124 the photoreceptors with which they later form synaptic networks to process visual stimuli⁴⁰. This raised
125 the possibility that photoreceptors themselves attract multipolar migrating HCs. To test this idea, we
126 interfered with photoreceptor-fate specification by CRISPR-mediated depletion of *Prdm1a* and *Prdm1b*
127 transcription factors^{39,41}. As for *vsx1+vsx2* KO, we analyzed the phenotypes directly in the F0
128 generation³⁷, using a pan-reporter for early neurogenic progenitors and different types of early neurons
129 *Tg(atoh7:gap-RFP)*, and a reporter for both HCs and early photoreceptors *Tg(lhx1:GFP)*^{27,39}.

130 Overall, retinal lamination in *prdm1a* KOs seemed similar to controls (Figures 1E, S1C). However,
131 *prdm1b* KOs displayed patches that were not occupied by photoreceptors in the most apical cell layer
132 (Figures 1E, S1D). These apical areas without photoreceptors were frequently occupied by ectopically
133 placed HCs. Live-imaging of the KO embryos in *Tg(atoh7:gap-RFP)*, labels photoreceptors) and
134 *Tg(lhx1:GFP)*, labels HCs) reporter lines confirmed that migrating HCs can overshoot apically to
135 positions where the photoreceptor layer was compromised (Video S3). We further noted a small but
136 reproducible number of HCs that did not migrate apically but remained within the AC-layer in *prdm1b*
137 KO embryos. Such ‘stuck HCs’ were not seen in control or in *scrambled* KOs (embryos injected with
138 RNPs carrying non-targeting gRNAs³⁷) (Figures 1F, S1D). This indicated that photoreceptors might
139 have some guiding effect on HC migration, however, this effect seemed relatively minor. In places in
140 which the photoreceptor layer was not formed, HCs overshoot their normal position and resided there.
141 Together, these experiments suggest that similar to basal retinal ganglion cells (Figure 1A) that were
142 reported to provide a physical stopping point for the HC initial basal movement³², photoreceptors
143 mainly serve as a physical barrier for HC apical migration in the developing zebrafish retina.

144

145 **Figure 1. Multipolar horizontal cell navigation is not affected by the absence of bipolar cells or an**
 146 **incomplete photoreceptor cell layer.**

147 **A)** Schematic of multipolar horizontal cell (HC, cyan) migration in the context of other laminating neurons,
 148 namely amacrine cells (AC, yellow), photoreceptors (magenta) and bipolar cells (purple) in the developing
 149 zebrafish retina. (hpf = hours post fertilization). See also Figure S1A.

150 **B)** Time series of HC (cyan and yellow; white arrow) multipolar migration from the basal AC layer (cyan and
 151 yellow) towards the photoreceptor layer until lamination below the photoreceptor layer (magenta). The retinal
 152 ganglion cell layer (yellow) resides below the ACs. *Tg(ato7:gap-RFP)* labels all retinal neurons except bipolar
 153 cells; *Tg(ptf1a:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP)* labels ACs and HCs and *Tg(crx:gap-CFP)* labels photoreceptors and faintly
 154 bipolar cells. Scale bars: 20 μ m. See also Video S1.

155 **C)** Lamination of bipolar cells (grey), ACs and HCs (yellow) in a 54 hpf retina. The photoreceptor layer is marked
 156 by the white dotted area. The magnified view of the retina on the right show migration of HCs (white arrows) in-
 157 between the neighboring bipolar cells. *Tg(vsx1:GFP)*, marks bipolar cells and *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* marks ACs and
 158 HCs. Scale bars: 20 μ m and 5 μ m, respectively.

159 **D)** HC and AC lamination at 80 hpf in a control embryo compared to a *vsx1+vsx2* F0 knockout (KO) embryo in
 160 which no bipolar cells form. In contrast to the control (i), the AC layer (yellow) in the KO embryo extends into
 161 the presumptive bipolar cell layer (ii) (areas indicated with dashed line). See also Figure S1B. *Tg(lhx1:GFP)*
 162 labels HCs and *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* both ACs and HCs. See also Video S2. Scale bars: 20 μ m.

163 E) HC (cyan; white arrows) migration in control and in *prdm1b* F0 KO embryo which shows depletion of
164 photoreceptors forming empty patches in the photoreceptor layer (magenta and yellow). Zpr-1 (antibody) labels
165 photoreceptors, *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* HCs and *Tg(ato7:gap-RFP)* both photoreceptors, HCs and retinal ganglion cells.
166 Scale bars: 20 μ m. See also Video S3 and Figure S1D.

167 F) Box plot quantification of horizontal cells more than 10 μ m away from the photoreceptor layer in laminated
168 retinae of different genetic conditions. Non-targeting guide RNAs were injected for control (*scrambled*) KO. $N =$
169 31 (control), 17 (*vsx1+vsx2*), 23 (*prdm1b*) retinae. P values (Mann-Whitney test versus (vs.) *scrambled* KO) =
170 0,0029 (*vsx1+vsx2*); <0,0001 (*prdm1b*). Quantifications performed on > 72 hpf KO embryos. Lower and upper
171 box hinges show 25th and 75th percentiles. Middle line = median; whiskers = minimum and maximum; dots =
172 individual measurements.

173

174 **In the absence of amacrine cells, horizontal cells fail to undergo multipolar apical migration.**

175 The data thus far strongly indicated that the lack of bipolar cells or photoreceptors does not massively
176 influence apical HC migration. Further, previous work from our group revealed that also retinal
177 ganglion cells, while they can act as a basal barrier, are dispensable for HCs to reach their final
178 position³². Thus, we examined whether the cells that surround the HCs at this developmental stage,
179 ACs, could be instructive for their movement as these cells physically intermingle with HCs before they
180 initiate their apical migration. ACs and HCs both initially use somal translocation to migrate basally
181 and then switch to a multipolar morphology within the AC-layer^{15,42}. Once in the AC-layer, multipolar
182 ACs laminate without substantial further movements. HCs stay within the AC-layer for up to 8 hours
183 before the onset of multipolar apical migration (Figures 1A-B). To test whether the neighboring ACs
184 contribute to the HC departure from the AC-layer, we used a combination of two well characterized
185 *Ptf1a* morpholinos (MO), that have been shown to remove almost all ACs and substantially decrease
186 the amount of HCs in the developing zebrafish retina^{43,44}. These morpholinos were injected in the
187 reporter line *Tg(lhx1:GFP); Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* labeling HCs and early photoreceptors (via *lhx1*) and
188 HCs and ACs (via *ptf1a*). In agreement with previous findings^{39,45}, the MO-treated retinae at 72 hpf
189 lacked almost all ACs and most HCs (Figure 2A). Remaining HCs in the MO-treated embryos, were
190 found basally at stages at which control HCs would have already undergone apical migration (Figure
191 2B). To confirm that the cells stuck in the AC layer were indeed HCs, we stained the morphant embryos
192 for transcription factor *Prox1* that labels both HCs and bipolar cells in the retina⁴⁶. This staining
193 confirmed that the cells seen in the presumptive AC-layer were indeed *Prox1*-positive HCs. These cells
194 located more basally than what is seen in controls of similar developmental stages (Figures 2A-B). Of
195 note, in such AC and HC depleted condition, we occasionally observed photoreceptors moving in a
196 multipolar manner into their respective cell layer, indicating that photoreceptors might turn to
197 multipolar migration when instead of ACs and HCs, excess photoreceptors are born³⁹ (Figure S1E).

198

199

200 **Figure 2. Horizontal cells fail to migrate towards the photoreceptor cell layer in the absence of amacrine**
201 **cells.**

202 **A)** HCs (cyan and yellow) and ACs (grey and yellow) in control and in embryos injected with Ptf1a morpholinos
203 (MO). *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* labels HCs and photoreceptors. *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* labels ACs and HCs. HuC/HuD (antibody,
204 grey) labels ACs and retinal ganglion cells. Scale bars: 20 μ m.

205 **B)** Ptf1a MO-treated retina labelled with Prox1 (antibody, yellow) that labels bipolar cells and HCs (cyan and
206 yellow, white arrows) at 72 hpf. *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* labels HCs and photoreceptors. Zoom-in of the area shown by
207 dashed white line. Nuclei were stained with DAPI (grey). Scale bars: 20 μ m and 10 μ m, respectively.

208 **C)** Schematics of transplantation of donor control cells into a Ptf1a MO-treated recipient embryo. Control cells
209 (cyan) from *Tg(lhx1:GFP); Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* donor embryos were aspirated and transplanted in different amounts
210 to the mid-blastula stage (3.5-4.5 hpf) of recipient embryos *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* (grey) injected at 1-cell stage with Ptf1a
211 MO. Transplanted control cells (cyan) in Ptf1a MO tissue surroundings were tracked throughout retinal
212 lamination.

213 **D)** Time series of control HC migration (cyan and yellow, white arrow) in a donor retina. The dotted lines indicate
214 the photoreceptor and AC-layers. Last picture of the panel shows the same retina at 72 hpf, with the white box

215 indicating the imaged area. HuC/HuD (antibody, grey) labels ACs and retinal ganglion cells. Scale bars: 5 μ m and
216 20 μ m, respectively. (See also Video S4).

217 **E)** Time series of control donor HC migration in a *Ptfla* MO-recipient retina. In contrast to the control HC
218 migration (Figure 2D), control HCs (cyan and yellow; white and grey arrows) transplanted into the *Ptfla*-MO
219 retina do not migrate towards the photoreceptor layer. The dotted lines indicate the photoreceptor and AC-layers.
220 The last panel shows the same retina at 72 hpf, with the white box indicating the imaged area. HuC/HuD (antibody,
221 grey) labels ACs and retinal ganglion cells. Scale bars: 10 μ m and 20 μ m respectively. (See also Video S4).

222 **F)** 72 hpf *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* *Ptfla* MO-injected recipient retinæ with increasing amounts of transplanted donor
223 control ACs (yellow) and HCs (cyan and yellow). White arrowheads label transplanted HCs that have successfully
224 laminated below the photoreceptors. *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* labels HCs, *Tg(ptfla:DsRed)* labels ACs and HCs. HuC/HuD
225 (antibody, grey) staining labels ACs and retinal ganglion cells. Scale bars: 20 μ m.

226

227

228 To further and more directly test how control HCs would behave in the absence of surrounding ACs,
229 we used transplantation assays. Different amounts of cells from *Tg(lhx1:GFP); Tg(ptfla:DsRed)* donor
230 embryos were transplanted into *Ptfla*-MO treated *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* recipient embryos (Figure 2C). When
231 imaging the transplanted embryos at 72 hpf, their retinæ had very little ACs or HCs, except for the few
232 transplanted cells. Live-imaging of these retinæ showed that, unlike in controls (Figure 2D, Video S4),
233 transplanted HCs in *Ptfla*-MO retinæ did not undergo apical migration. While cells could still move,
234 these movements now occurred horizontally within the presumptive AC-layer (Figure 2E, Video S4).
235 Leveraging the possibility of transplanting different amounts of control cells into the *Ptfla*-morphants,
236 we asked whether the number of ACs in the vicinity of HCs could influence the efficiency of apical HC
237 migration. We indeed observed that in 72 hpf retinæ, in which only few ACs and HCs were
238 transplanted, HCs remained in the AC-layer and did not manage to move towards the photoreceptor
239 layer. However, with increasing numbers of transplanted ACs that surrounded HCs, HCs managed to
240 leave the presumptive AC-layer. In this case, HCs were often able to laminate below the photoreceptors
241 (Figure 2F). This indicated a relationship between the amount of ACs present in close vicinity or in
242 contact to HCs, and the ability of HCs to initiate multipolar apical movement. Overall, whereas bipolar
243 cells appeared to have no impact, and the photoreceptor layer seemed to mainly serve as a steric
244 hindrance to stop apical HC translocation, the presence of ACs surrounding HCs most likely played a
245 more significant role for the initiation of HC multipolar apical migration.

246

247 **Transcriptomic analysis combined with high-content in vivo knockout screen reveals candidate**
248 **genes instructing horizontal cell migration.**

249 We have thus far demonstrated that a small but consistent number of HCs do not apically migrate when
250 photoreceptor layer formation was disrupted (Figures 1F, S1D), and that HCs fail to move apically
251 when lacking surrounding ACs (Figure 2F). Both of these observations argue that interactions between
252 HC and ACs and possibly also HCs and photoreceptors, steer multipolar HCs out of the AC-layer and

253 towards the photoreceptor layer. Previous work showed that neither stiffness gradients nor fibrous
254 ECM-mediated guidance are likely candidates to navigate this migration as neither are present within
255 the developing inner nuclear layer³². Thus, we speculated that HC navigation from the basal AC-layer
256 to more apical positions beneath the photoreceptor layer, was steered by cell-cell signaling based
257 mechanisms between ACs and HCs and photoreceptors and HCs, respectively.

258 To find potential signaling cues that navigate HC migration, we performed a transcriptome analysis. To
259 this end, we dissected retinæ from a *Tg(lhx1:GFP); Tg(ptfla:DsRed)* reporter line at 38 hpf, when the
260 majority of the HCs are moving basally together with ACs, at 48 hpf when HCs are enriched basally in
261 the AC-layer and at 58 hpf when most HCs undergo apical migration towards the photoreceptor layer¹⁵
262 (Figure S1A). Next, we sorted the three retinal cell types, HC, AC and photoreceptors based on the
263 specificity of *lhx1:GFP* (for photoreceptors and HCs) and *ptfla:DsRed* (for HCs and ACs) fluorescent
264 reporters (Figure 3A). Differential expression analysis (DESeq2, P-value <0.05, log₂ fold change >1)
265 was performed on RNA sequencing data (European Nucleotide Archive, PRJEB80557) of four
266 biological replicates per developmental stage. This enabled us to specifically probe for up- or
267 downregulated genes that change between ACs and HCs and between photoreceptors and HCs, during
268 the different phases of HC migration.

269 For the analysis of emerging candidates and their possible effects on HC migration, we performed an
270 in vivo F0 CRISPR screen, analyzing over 200 knockout embryos per candidate gene (Figure 3A). This
271 F0 CRISPR approach, was similar to the *vsx1+vsx2* and *prdm1b* knock outs (Figures 1D-E) as it also
272 used three guide RNAs (gRNAs) per gene to achieve a high number of biallelic knockouts³⁷. To
273 accurately assess the penetrance and phenotypic variability of the knockouts, we employed automated
274 high-content imaging of 72 hpf F0 KO embryos using specialized 96-well plates designed for uniform
275 embryo alignment.

276 As a positive control, we targeted the *oncut1* gene, that had already been shown to be involved in HC
277 differentiation in mouse and chick⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹. As expected, *oncut1* showed high expression in HCs in our
278 transcriptomic analysis at all three developmental stages, most prominently at 38 hpf (Figure S2A).
279 Three gRNAs targeting different *oncut1* loci were pooled, complexed with Cas9 and injected as RNPs
280 into the *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* [photoreceptors, HCs]; *ptfla:DsRed* [ACs, HCs]) reporter line. We found that
281 similar to *Oncut1*^{-/-} mice^{47,48}, *oncut1* KO zebrafish larvae, showed no or very few HCs at 72 hpf,
282 whereas retinal lamination appeared otherwise comparable to the *scrambled* KO controls (Figure S2B).
283 Based on this successful proof of principle approach, we manually screened candidates from the
284 DeSeg2-filtered dataset (Data file S1). Building on the fact that neither ECM components, nor
285 mechanosensing or integrin-based migration³² were important for HC migration, we initially
286 concentrated on genes upregulated in HCs and more broadly associated with non-fibrous ECM
287 components or changes in cell-cell adhesion.

288 The F0 KO embryos depleted for genes of these three categories, showed phenotypes from no
289 discernible differences to controls to scenarios in which some HCs remained in the AC-layer. The latter

290 included genes encoding Protocadherin 8 (*pcdh8*), Protocadherin γ cluster (*pcdh-\gamma*) and DS cell
 291 adhesion molecule like 1 (*dscaml1*) (Figure S5). Other F0 KO, for example for the ECM glycoproteins
 292 Tenascin C (*tnc*) or Tenascin R (*tnr*), showed more general phenotypes effecting overall retina
 293 lamination. This initial screen demonstrated that coupling transcriptomics analysis with F0 KO
 294 screening platform offers a straightforward pipeline to extract functional relevance from the
 295 transcriptomics data. It also provided some insights into possible HC self-avoidance^{50,51} and a role for
 296 non-fibrous ECM in retinal lamination. However, this filtering approach was not yet sufficient to reveal
 297 specific candidates for cell-cell signaling based mechanisms occurring between HCs, ACs and
 298 photoreceptors that could contribute to HC apical multipolar navigation. Therefore, we redirected our
 299 investigations to find a pipeline that allowed us to specifically screen for signaling-related targets.

300
 301 **Figure 3. Transcriptomics analysis of photoreceptors, horizontal- and amacrine cells combined with high-**
 302 **content knockout screen to identify candidates guiding HC navigation.**

303 **A)** Schematic of the pipeline to extract ligand-receptor based guidance cues in horizontal cell migration. Collected
 304 retinae from *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* [photoreceptors, HCs]; *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* [ACs, HCs] embryos at 38, 48 and 58 hpf
 305 (1.) were dissociated into single cells (2.) and sorted based on their fluorescence signature (3.). Four biological
 306 replicates were used per each stage. The derived RNAseq data (4.) was analyzed with zebrafish-adapted NATMI
 307 analysis to elucidate repulsive and attractive ligand-receptor candidates between AC-HC and HC-photoreceptor

308 (PR) cell pairs (5.). Shortlisted candidates were tested via a high-throughput in vivo CRISPR screen (6.) (See also
309 Data file S1).

310 **B)** Heatmap visualization of the NATMI analysis (Log₂ mean-expression weight) of repulsive and attractive
311 ligand-receptor candidates between HCs and ACs as well as HCs and photoreceptors (PR) at 38, 48 and 58 hpf.
312 In AC-HC, HC-AC, HC-PR and PR-HC columns, the first nominator is for the specific ligand and second for
313 corresponding receptor expressed in that cell type. The ligand-receptor candidates with the largest changes in the
314 expression weights between the time points and/or cell pairs, are shown in bold (See also Data file S3).

315

316

317 **NATMI analysis uncovers specific repulsive and attractive ligand-receptor interactions for**
318 **horizontal cell migration.**

319 To identify secreted or contact-dependent up or downregulation of AC- or photoreceptor-derived
320 ligands that could interact with receptors expressed in HCs, we screened for altered expression levels
321 of such factors between 38 hpf - 48 hpf or 48 hpf - 58 hpf time-points using a NATMI toolkit. This
322 toolkit predicts cell-cell communication networks using a database (connectome) of 2,293 ligand-
323 receptor pairs, curated based on published studies⁵². As the original connectome was designed for
324 mouse and human expression datasets, we created a zebrafish connectome using the NCBI homologue
325 and ZFIN human and zebrafish orthology datasets, with help of the authors of the original study⁵² (Data
326 file S2). Results of the zebrafish connectome-based NATMI analysis were inspected for repulsive and
327 attractive ligand-receptor pairs (Data file S3). When analyzing the heatmaps of filtered expression
328 weights (Log₂ multiplied expression of average ligand and receptor counts⁵²), the repulsive Slit1b-
329 Robo2 and Slit2-Robo2 pairs between ACs (ligand) and HCs (receptor) clearly stood out (Figures 3B,
330 S2C). Both *slit1b/slit2* and *robo2* expressions peaked at the 48 hpf, matching the onset of HC apical
331 migration. In comparison, neither *slit3* with documented roles outside the CNS nor *slit1a* or *robo1*,
332 which can also drive Slit-mediated repulsion in axon guidance⁵³⁻⁵⁵, showed notable basal expression or
333 upregulation across the three developmental time points. This indicated specificity of the detected
334 receptor ligand pairs. In addition, two secreted semaphorin 3 class ligands (Sema3aa and Sema3fb) with
335 several possible receptor candidates, appeared as potential guidance molecules between ACs and HCs.
336 These most likely would serve as repulsive cues as shown for migrating cortical interneurons^{56,57}
337 (Figures S2C-D). However, their expression weight differences between the three developmental time
338 points were not as pronounced as for Slit1b/2-Robo2. Additionally, depending on the receptor pairing,
339 they displayed upregulation or uniformly high expression across the three time-points also between
340 photoreceptors and HCs. We thus did not perform an in-depth analysis for the role of class 3
341 semaphorins for HC migration as we also noted that the *sema3aa+sema3fb* F0 KO showed only a mild
342 phenotype for HC basal retention (Figure S5).

343 Analysis of NATMI predictions for interactions between photoreceptors (ligand) and HCs (receptor)
344 revealed the glial cell-line derived neurotrophic factor (GDNF) family member Neurturin (*nrtin*) and

345 Gfr α 1a/Ret receptors⁵⁸ as well as Neurotrophin-3 (NT-3, *ntf3*) and Ntrk3a receptor⁵⁹, as most prominent
346 candidates (Figure 3B). To date, both NT-3 and GDNF family members have been mainly studied in
347 the context of cell migration in the peripheral nervous system development with Neurturin additionally
348 reported as a potential protective factor for neurodegenerative disorders⁶⁰⁻⁶⁴. Similar to *slit1b* and *slit2*
349 in ACs, *nrtin* and *ntf3* expression peaked at 48 hpf in photoreceptors. Further, their corresponding
350 receptors *gfra1a*, *ret* and *ntrk3a* also reached peak expression in HCs at the same developmental stage.
351 Together, the NATMI analysis optimized for the zebrafish dataset, enabled the extraction of possible
352 repulsive signaling molecules between the ACs and HCs as well as ligand-receptor pairs linked to
353 attractive signaling expressed between photoreceptors and HCs that we tested further using our F0
354 CRISPR screen.

355

356 **Slit1b/Slit2 and Robo2 guide horizontal cell demixing from the amacrine cell layer.**

357 Slits are able to instruct axon guidance by repelling Robo-expressing neuronal growth cones both in
358 invertebrates and vertebrates⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷. In the context of axon guidance in the developing retina, Slit1b/2-
359 Robo2 pairs are important cues for directing retinal ganglion cells' axons towards the brain⁶⁸⁻⁷⁰. In
360 addition to axonogenesis, Slit-Robo signaling has been suggested to be involved in guidance of non-
361 neuronal cell types such as the neural crest cells and leukocytes^{71,72} but to the best of our knowledge,
362 the direct involvement of Slit1/2-Robo2 repulsive interactions have not been shown for migrating
363 neurons in vivo.

364 Based on our NATMI analysis, Slit1b and Slit2 expression upregulation in ACs coincided with
365 upregulated Robo2 expression in HCs when they are to leave the AC-layer^{15,25} (Figures 3B, S1A). To
366 confirm that these repulsive candidates were indeed expressed in the developing retina at the stages
367 relevant for HC migration, we performed in situ hybridization for Slit2 and Robo2 mRNA using
368 wholemount and sectioned embryos (Figures S3A-B). At 38 hpf Slit2 mRNA signal was observed in
369 the optic nerve. From 48 hpf onwards, and in line with previous literature^{69,70}, AC-layer specific Slit2
370 signal was increasing, becoming more pronounced by 58 hpf. For Robo2 mRNA expression, no retinal
371 signal was observed at 38 hpf. At 48 hpf, Robo2 mRNA was detected in the retinal ganglion cell layer,
372 alongside a faint signal seen in the AC-layer. By 58 hpf, the Robo2 signal in the retinal ganglion cell
373 layer became more prominent. At 58 hpf Robo2 signal was also seen within the inner nuclear layer,
374 including the HC-cell layer. This is similar to the published data of older larvae, additionally reporting
375 absence of other Robo receptors 1,3 and 4 within the retinal inner nuclear layer⁶⁹. Negative control
376 sense probes for Slit2 and Robo2 showed no signal (Figures S3A-B).

377 Cells can use different types of protrusions to probe their surroundings for attachment or as a readout
378 for signaling cues like Slit2, at least *in vitro*⁷³⁻⁷⁵. As migrating HCs extend multiple protrusions^{32,76}, we
379 asked whether Robo2 receptor could localize to these structures. Antibody staining showed Robo2
380 protein both at the plasma membrane as well as in protrusions of HCs undergoing multipolar apical
381 migration (Figure S3C). Further, live-imaging of a UAS:Robo2-mCherry construct in the

382 *Tg(ptf1a:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP* [ACs, HCs]) reporter line, revealed dynamic localization of Robo2-
383 puncta in HC protrusions (Figure S3D and Video S5). Thus, beside residing in the plasma membrane,
384 Robo2 localized in the protrusions of multipolar migrating HCs.

385 After confirming Slit2 and Robo2 expression in the retina and Robo2 protein localization in HCs and
386 their protrusions, we probed a direct role for Slit-Robo signaling in apical HC migration. To this end,
387 we generated F0 KO embryos targeting both *slit1b* and *slit2*, *robo2*, or a combination of both
388 *slits+robo2* together (Figures 4A, S3E-F) and performed an in vivo screen for these KOs as described
389 above (Figures 3A, S2A). Knocking out either the Slit1b and Slit2 ligands or Robo2 receptor, caused a
390 large fraction of HCs to remain in the AC-layer at 72 hpf, while in the *scrambled* KO embryos, HC
391 lamination was complete at this stage (Figure 4B). Targeting Robo2 mRNA with a validated splice-
392 blocking morpholino⁷⁷, recapitulated the *robo2* F0 KO phenotype (Figure S3G).

393 To further confirm that the effect is specific for Robo2 depletion, we generated *robo2* F1 adults in which
394 deletions in the *robo2* gene lead to a premature stop codon (Data file S4). Retinae of Robo2 mutant
395 embryos displayed similar numbers of HCs remaining in the AC-layer as the *robo2* F0 KOs (Figures
396 4A-B, S3E). This phenotype was lost when introducing a functional copy of the gene through an
397 outcross with the wildtype line into the Robo2 mutant background.

398 Since Slit1b and Slit2 both work through Robo2, and Robo2 loss caused the strongest phenotype with
399 around half of the HCs failing to laminate beneath the photoreceptor layer (Figure 4B), we focused on
400 Robo2 to investigate the role of Slit-Robo-signaling in HC migration. In Robo2 mutants, a similar
401 number of ectopically placed HCs as in 72 hpf larvae, was found in the AC-layer even at 5 days post
402 fertilization (dpf) (Figures 4A, 4C). Interestingly, these ectopic cells showed morphologies typical for
403 laminated HCs as indicated by their flat nuclei. This suggests that misplaced HCs cannot be rescued
404 over development and do not undergo apoptosis even when misplaced in the tissue.

405 Overall, the lack of Slit1b/2-Robo2 interaction, impaired apical migration of around half of the HCs,
406 demonstrating that repulsive Slit-Robo signaling, potentially sensed through HC protrusions,
407 significantly impacts the process of HC departure from the AC-layer.

408

409 **Figure 4. Lack of Slit-Robo impairs horizontal cell migration towards the photoreceptor cell layer.**

410 A) 72 hpf retinæ from *scrambled*, *slit1b+slit2* F0, and *robo2* F0 as well as *robo2* F1 KO embryos. Whereas in
 411 *scrambled* KO all HCs (cyan) migrated to locations below the photoreceptor layer (dotted line with arrows) to
 412 form the HC-layer (dense dotted line with arrows), knocking out either *slit1b+slit2* ligands or the *robo2* receptor

413 results in HCs remaining within the AC layer (white line with arrows). The stable *robo2* KO line (*robo2* F1)
414 phenocopies the *robo2* F0 phenotype. *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* labels the HCs. (See also Figure S3E). Scale bars: 20 μ m.

415 **B)** Box plot quantification of HCs remaining in the AC layer (more than 10 μ m away from the photoreceptors) in
416 *scrambled*, *slit1b+slit2* and *robo2* KO and *robo2* F1 larvae as well as in larvae from an outcross (oX) of the *robo2*
417 F1 line with wildtype control. (See also Figure 1F). $N = 31$ (*scrambled*), 33 (*slit1b+slit2*), 9 (*robo2* F0), 43 (*robo2*
418 F1), 10 (*robo2* F1 oX) retinæ. Quantifications performed on >72 hpf larvae.

419 P values (Mann-Whitney test vs. Scrambled KO) = <0,0001 (*slit1b+slit2*); <0,0001 (*robo2* F0), <0,0001 (*robo2*
420 F1), 0,05 (*robo2* F1 oX wildtype). Lower and upper box hinges show 25th and 75th percentiles. Middle line =
421 median; whiskers = minimum and maximum; dots = individual measurements.

422 **C)** Ectopically placed HCs in the AC-layer (cyan and yellow) in a 5 day (120 hpf) old *robo2* F1 knockout larvae.
423 The lower panel shows super-resolution (Airyscan) images of the *robo2* F1 retinal laminar layers at 120 hpf. Grey
424 arrows label examples of ectopically positioned HCs (cyan and yellow) within the AC-layer. HCs show flat
425 nuclear morphology compared to ACs (yellow) that show more rounded nuclei (white arrows). *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)*
426 labels ACs and HCs. *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* labels HCs and DRAQ5 (grey) labels nuclei. Scale bars: 20 μ m and 10 μ m,
427 respectively.

428 **D)** Montage of a time-lapse image series of HC (cyan and yellow) migration in a *slit2+robo2* F0 knockout embryo.
429 Two HCs that undergo mitosis as they migrate, are labelled (white and grey arrows) and the two sister cells are
430 followed after division. Scale bars: 5 μ m. (See also Video S6 and Figure S3F).

431 **E)** Violin plot quantification of the positions at which HCs divide in *scrambled* KO (blue) and in *robo2* F1 (purple)
432 embryos. Division positions are plotted in respect to the distance (μ m) to the photoreceptor layer. $N = 67$
433 (*scrambled* KO), 75 (*robo2* F1) cytokinesis events tracked from 6 *scrambled* and 6 *robo2* F1 embryos. P value
434 (Mann-Whitney test) = <0,001. Dashed line = median, dotted lines = quartiles, dots = individual measurements.

435 **F)** Box plot of the division distance (μ m) (see Figure 4E) versus the resulting sister HCs final laminar location in
436 *scrambled* KO (blue) and in *robo2* F1 (purple) embryos. 0/2 = both sisters laminate correctly below the
437 photoreceptor layer. 2/2 = both sisters remain within the AC-layer. $N = 67$ (*scrambled* KO), 75 (*robo2* F1) division
438 events. Lower and upper box hinges show 25th and 75th percentiles. Middle line = median; whiskers = minimum
439 and maximum; dots = individual measurements.

440

441

442 **Upon Slit-Robo downregulation, signaling from the photoreceptor cell layer becomes critical for** 443 **HC apical arrival.**

444 We noted that while half of the HCs remain in the AC-layer and do not correctly laminate in the *Slit1b/2*
445 and *Robo2* knockout embryos, the other half still managed to reach the photoreceptor layer. HC
446 morphology in control- versus *robo2* KO embryos was similar for cells remaining in the AC-layer and
447 for cells correctly laminating beneath photoreceptors (Figures 4A, 4C, S1A). This suggested that the
448 HCs that reach the photoreceptor layer do so in a similar manner as seen in the control condition. Each
449 HC undergo a terminal division during migration that in principle can occur along the inner nuclear
450 layer but shows a strong preference to occur close to the photoreceptor layer²⁵. When analyzing HC
451 division positions in *robo2* KO, we noted that whereas in *scrambled* KO most divisions occurred close

452 to the photoreceptor layer as previously seen in control retinæ²⁵, many HCs in the *Robo2* mutant
453 embryos divided at more basal positions within the inner nuclear layer (Figure 4E). To analyze the
454 behavior of sister HC upon division and probe whether position division could be correlated with the
455 possibility of HCs to still reach the photoreceptor layer, we performed live imaging of HC sister cells
456 in *slit2+robo2* KO embryos. We found that in both *robo2* and *slit2+robo2* KOs, sister HCs that, after
457 division, located closer to the photoreceptor layer, were more likely to laminate correctly while HCs
458 remaining at more basal positions after division, mostly moved away from the photoreceptor layer,
459 towards the ACs (Figure 4D, Video S6). This is different in the *scrambled* KO control situation where
460 both sister cells move towards and laminate below the photoreceptor layer (Video S6). Moreover, for
461 divisions that occurred more basally in the inner nuclear layer ($> 20 \mu\text{m}$ from photoreceptors), it became
462 more likely that both sister cells fail to migrate apically and end up staying within the AC-layer (Figure
463 4F). These data suggest that whereas *Slit1b/2-Robo2* between ACs and HCs is a strong component to
464 send HCs in apical direction, additional cues could influence HC navigation towards photoreceptors if
465 the cells locate close enough to the photoreceptor layer.

466

467 **Neurturin provides an attractive signaling cue to guide multipolar horizontal cells towards the**
468 **photoreceptor cell layer.**

469 Knockout of *robo2*, *slit2* or their combination, did not fully disrupt HC apical multipolar migration and
470 HCs that divided closer to the photoreceptor layer were still able to laminate correctly (Figures 4A-F).
471 Further, we observed that migrating multipolar HCs frequently extend protrusions towards the
472 photoreceptor layer as also seen in developing mouse retinæ^{30,76} (Video S1). This protrusive activity
473 was also observed in *slit2+robo2* KO retinæ (Video S6). As we further noted that *Robo2* localized to
474 the HC protrusions (Figures S3C-D), we analyzed these HC protrusions in detail. Control HCs
475 undergoing multipolar apical migration showed that these, often branched, protrusions were enriched
476 with F-actin and frequently contacted the photoreceptor layer (Figures 5A-B). Further, 3D-imaging the
477 retinæ of 52-54 hpf *Tg(lhx1:GFP); Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* and *Tg(ptf1a:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP)* reporter lines
478 subjected to expansion microscopy^{78,79}, showed that the HC protrusions can extend in-between the
479 neighboring cells (Figure 5C) and apical-oriented protrusions reach and connect with the photoreceptor
480 layer (Figure S4A and Video S7). Overall, this data indicated that HC protrusions in the vicinity of
481 photoreceptors or touching the photoreceptor layer, could sense a photoreceptor-derived signal that
482 could act at short scales and allow cells to reach apical locations beneath the photoreceptor layer.

483

484 **Figure 5. Multipolar horizontal cells use complex protrusions and navigate along amacrine cell-mediated**
485 **repulsive and photoreceptor cell-secreted attractive guidance cues within the crowded retinal tissue.**

486 **A)** Actin chromobody(CB)-labelled F-actin (UAS:ActinCB-TagGFP2 injected with *ptf1a:Gal4*, cyan) in HCs
487 migrating in 54 hpf retina. Dashed line indicates the photoreceptor layer. Nuclei were stained with DAPI (grey).
488 Scale bar: 5 μ m.

489 **B)** HCs (cyan) migrating towards the photoreceptors (magenta) in a 54 hpf retina showing retinal ganglion cells
490 (yellow) and ACs (cyan). The magnified area (white dashed line) shows an HC with two protrusions (white
491 arrows) contacting the photoreceptors. (See also Figure 1B and Video S1) *Tg(atoh7:gap-RFP, yellow)*,
492 *Tg(ptf1a:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP, cyan)*, *Tg(crx:gap-CFP, magenta)*. Scale bars: 20 μ m and 10 μ m respectively.

493 C) Close-ups from 52 hpf retinae after expansion microscopy. First panel (i) shows 3D-surface rendering of HCs
494 (cyan) expressing membrane *Tg(ptf1a:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP)* signal with long protrusions touching the
495 photoreceptor layer (white dashed line). The second panel (ii) shows HCs (fire) in between neighboring cells and
496 their nuclei (blue) with F-actin (white) seen at the cell-cell contacts. Magnification of the boxed area shows one
497 HC protrusion (fire) extending between the two cells labelled with F-actin (white). Nuclei were stained with DAPI.
498 Scale bars: 20 μm . See also Video S7 and Figure S4A.

499 D) *prdm1b* KO-mediated photoreceptor depletion in a *robo2* F1 background. Areas with a more intact
500 photoreceptor layer (white line) reproduce the *robo2* KO phenotype. In areas with absent or abnormal
501 photoreceptor layer (dashed line), a majority of HCs remain in the AC-layer. Two magnified areas (white boxes),
502 show examples of the lamination in parts of the retina with more intact (i) and more disrupted (ii) photoreceptor
503 layer. *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed, yellow)* labels ACs and HCs whereas *Tg(lhx1:GFP, cyan)* labels the HCs. Nuclei were
504 stained with DAPI (grey). See also Figure 1E for *Prdm1b* KO in control background. Scale bars: 20 μm .

505 E) Neurturin (*nrtin + nrtin-like*) KO in a *Robo2* F1 background results in a majority of HCs (cyan and yellow)
506 remaining in the AC layer. The AC layer (yellow) as well as other retinal layers appear as in control. (See also
507 Figures S4B, S4D and Video S8). Scale bars: 20 μm .

508 F) Box plot quantification of HCs remaining in the AC layer after the depletion of attractive cues. *ntf3* = NT-3,
509 *nrtin + nrtin-like* = Neurturin. $N = 31$ (*scrambled*), 15 (NT-3), 17 (*nrtin + nrtin-like*), 43 (*robo2* F1), 13 (*prdm1b* KO
510 in *Robo2* F1), 32 (*ntf3* KO in *Robo2* F1), 28 (*nrtin + nrtin-like* KO in *robo2* F1) retinae. Quantifications performed
511 on >72 hpf KO larvae. For *prdm1b* KO in *robo2* F1, only areas with disrupted photoreceptor layer were quantified.
512 P values (Mann-Whitney test) = 0.3531 (*ntf3* KO vs. *scrambled* KO), 0,0684 (*nrtin + nrtin-like* KO vs. *scrambled*
513 KO), <0,0001 (*robo2* F1 vs. *scrambled* KO), <0,0001 (*prdm1b* KO in *robo2* F1 vs. *robo2* F1), <0,0001 (*nrtin +*
514 *nrtin-like* KO in *robo2* F1 vs. *robo2* F1), <0,0001 (*ntf3* KO in *robo2* F1 vs. *robo2* F1), 0,7037 (*prdm1b* KO vs.
515 *nrtin + nrtin-like* KO in *robo2* F1). Lower and upper box hinges show 25th and 75th percentiles. Middle line =
516 median; whiskers = minimum and maximum; dots = individual measurements.

517 G) Schematic of the repulsive and attractive guidance cues working in concert to guide multipolar horizontal cell
518 navigation. At 48 hpf, ACs (yellow) start to express *Slit1b* and *Slit2* (red) to repulse *Robo2* expressing HCs (cyan)
519 towards the photoreceptors (magenta). At the same time, photoreceptors initiate expression of secreted Neurturins
520 (brown), to further attract HCs towards the photoreceptor layer, likely through the *Gfr α 1a* receptor.

521

522

523 Combining this idea with the finding that partial removal of photoreceptors in *prdm1b* KOs caused a
524 small but reproducible proportion of HCs to remain in the AC-layer (Figure 1F, S1D), we speculated
525 that in addition to *Slit-Robo* repulsion in the AC-layer, some additive instructive signaling could be
526 coming from photoreceptors to guide the last phase of apical HC migration. To test this idea, we
527 knocked out *prdm1b* in the *Robo2* mutant embryos to generate apical foci devoid of photoreceptors
528 (Figure 5D) as seen in *prdm1b* single KO (Figure 1E). In this condition, areas showing a control-like
529 photoreceptor layer also showed a similar ratio of HCs still laminating beneath this layer as seen in
530 *Robo2* mutant embryos. However, in areas with compromised photoreceptor layer, the majority of the
531 HCs remained in the AC-layer and no HC made it to apical positions (Figure 5D). As this strongly

532 indicated a role for one or multiple photoreceptor-derived signaling component(s) for successful HC
533 apical migration, we once more consulted our NATMI analysis. Consequently, we removed the two
534 most prominent attractive signaling candidates Neurturin (*nrtn*) and NT-3 (*ntf3*) (Figure 3B). For
535 complete Neurturin removal (Neurturin KO), we targeted *nrtn* jointly with Neurturin like (*nrtn-like*)
536 gene (*FO834855.1*) (Figure S4B). In control embryos, neither the absence of Neurturin or NT-3 ligands,
537 nor their putative receptors (*Gfr α 1a* or *Ntrk3a*, respectively), had a detectable effect on HC multipolar
538 apical migration (Figure S4C). We then removed the two attractive ligands in *Robo2* mutant embryos.
539 Knocking out *ntf3* in *Robo2* mutants did not show any additive effect and resulted in a similar number
540 of laminated and AC-layer remaining HCs as observed in the *Robo2* mutant background alone (Figures
541 S3E, S4D).

542 However, knockout of Neurturin in *Robo2* mutant embryos, generated a more profound effect on HCs
543 apical migration than seen in any other condition. Whereas the general retinal architecture appeared
544 intact, nearly all HCs remained in the AC-layer at 80 hpf (Figure 5E). Live imaging of the Neurturin
545 KO in *Robo2* mutants further demonstrated that the majority of the HCs only move within the AC-layer
546 and do not reach more apical positions (Video S8). A similar phenotype was observed when both
547 Neurturin and Neurturin-like were depleted through morpholino approaches (Neurturin MO) in the
548 *Robo2* mutant embryos (Figure S4E). Quantifying the HCs remaining in the AC-layer in response to
549 these KOs, provided further evidence that while depleting photoreceptors or Neurturin in control
550 embryos had little effect on HC navigation, in embryos lacking *Robo2* these factors become critical to
551 steer HC apical migration for the cells that made it close enough to the apical photoreceptors (Figure
552 5F).

553 Taken together, this shows that emerging Slit-Robo interaction between ACs and HCs at 48 hpf
554 provides strong apical-directed repulsion for HCs to leave the AC layer. Concurrently, photoreceptor-
555 derived Neurturin further attracts HCs, most likely through *Gfr α 1a* as pinpointed by our NATMI
556 analysis, towards the photoreceptor layer (Figure 5G). Therefore, spatially distinct yet concurrently
557 upregulated repulsive and attractive guidance cues steer the multipolar migration of multipolar
558 migrating HCs in the developing vertebrate retina.

559

560

561 **Discussion**

562

563 Multipolar neuronal migration is an evolutionary conserved, yet still poorly understood mode of cell
564 movement in the developing central nervous system. We here investigated this migration mode in the
565 developing zebrafish retina, focusing on the lamination of HC interneurons. By combining
566 transcriptomics approaches with high-content in vivo knockout screens and high-resolution in vivo
567 imaging, we reveal repulsive and attractive cues that collectively ensure the coordinated lamination of

568 these multipolar migrating neurons. We find that HC migration is only mildly affected by a disorganized
569 photoreceptor layer or the absence of bipolar cells. However, loss of the neighboring ACs at early
570 developmental stages when both cell types inhabit the lower inner nuclear layer, hampers HC apical
571 migration towards the photoreceptors.

572 We further discovered that HC apical movement requires the expression of repulsive Slit ligands by
573 ACs, which are sensed by Robo2 receptors on HCs. After exiting the AC layer, photoreceptor-derived
574 attractive Neurturin further ensures robust HC guidance towards photoreceptors. While this signaling
575 cue is weaker in the control situation, when Slit-Robo signaling is impaired, the attractive input from
576 the photoreceptor layer becomes increasingly critical for proper HC lamination. Together, our findings
577 show that environmental cues from neighboring cells can guide multipolar migration independently of
578 cellular scaffolds, a concept most likely conserved in other regions of the developing central nervous
579 system.

580

581 Previous studies in the rodent neocortex have provided important insights into the general dynamics of
582 multipolar migration and identified some of the molecular players involved in the transition from
583 multipolar to bipolar migration along radial glia cells^{15,25,32,80-83}. Unlike tangential or radial migrating
584 cells that largely rely on physical interaction with their neighbors and travel longer distances, multipolar
585 migration in the neocortex appears slower, covers smaller areas and is less dependent on direct contact
586 with surrounding cells^{10,11,80,13}. These studies, primarily conducted using ex vivo organotypic brain
587 slices, have thus led to the idea that multipolar migration represents a transient “waiting lounge” phase,
588 occurring at specific foci with permissible tissue composition. It was postulated that the multipolar
589 phase mainly helps cells to passively disperse until they receive cues that trigger their transition into
590 bipolar migration or the establish neuronal connections.

591 However, data from our lab and others argue that this might be a reductionist view that does not hold
592 true in all circumstances. In the developing zebrafish retina, HCs can display dynamic space adaptation
593 to efficiently move through the inner nuclear layer, packed with neighboring cells^{25,32}. It was further
594 demonstrated that HCs successfully laminate even when particular cell types are removed and
595 compensated for by other cells as seen for retinal ganglion cell removal³², bipolar cell removal (this
596 study) and upon partial photoreceptor removal (this study). These results indicate that HCs do not rely
597 on specific neighboring neurons, at least as scaffolds, to reach their correct laminar position. Moreover,
598 most HCs still move towards their final target zone when overall tissue stiffness is increased, even
599 though increasing tissue stiffness seems to make it harder for cells to migrate^{32,84}. Together, these
600 findings demonstrate that neither disruptions in physical interaction with the canonical neighboring
601 neurons, nor changes in tissue mechanical parameters, significantly hinder HCs’ ability to achieve
602 proper lamination.

603 Additional support for the feasibility of multipolar migration to overcome local cell- or tissue-scale
604 constraints, stems from the fact that other retinal cell types, photoreceptors and retinal ganglion cells,

605 can also adopt multipolar mode of movement in situations when their primary movement mechanism
606 is challenged. Both photoreceptors and retinal ganglion cells canonically undergo bipolar somal
607 translocation guided by their apical and/or basal processes⁸⁵. However, when their basal process
608 reattachment is compromised, retinal ganglion cells successfully laminate using multipolar migration²⁶.
609 Similarly, in *Ptf1a* morphants where excess photoreceptors are generated³⁹ and ACs and HCs are largely
610 absent, photoreceptors can adopt a multipolar migration mode to reach the outer retina (this study). This
611 likely reflects that multipolar movement, in what is probably a more crowded environment, becomes
612 more effective than somal translocation.

613 Together, these findings strongly argue that multipolar migration is not only a passive, transient
614 “waiting lounge” phase dictated by permissive tissue microenvironments, as previously suggested.
615 Instead, we propose that multipolar migration can serve as a robust and adaptive mechanism for
616 neuronal positioning, particularly when other ways of movements become less efficient. While our
617 observations are centered on the retina, this adaptability is likely also present in other regions of the
618 developing brain. Additional studies on different brain regions are needed to fully characterize the
619 capacity and constraints of multipolar migration. Such insights would be relevant for a better
620 understanding of neurodevelopmental malformations, for example microcephaly and posterior
621 pachygyria, caused by impaired suspension of the multipolar migration phase in cortical development⁵.

622
623 HCs multipolar movement seems efficient despite being independent of cellular scaffolds like ECM
624 and neighboring cells that guide radial and tangential migration³². These cells instead seem to orient by
625 extrinsic signaling molecules as revealed in this study. When HCs lack the surrounding ACs, we noticed
626 the strongest HC basal retention, only matched by the joint removal of *Neurturin-Gfr α 1a* and *Slit1b/2-
627 Robo2* cues. This strong phenotype could imply that additional interactions take place between the ACs
628 and HCs that further help HCs to demix from the AC-layer. Live-imaging of *Robo2-* and
629 *Neurturin+Robo2* depleted embryos showed that HCs that fail to laminate nevertheless initially move
630 towards the top of the AC layer but later translocate or are displaced back basally. One possible
631 explanation for this behavior could be a potential difference of cortical tension between ACs or HCs
632 that could promote HC apical movement out of the AC layer⁸⁶. Another interesting possibility to
633 facilitate HC-AC demixing could be a differential expression of specific protocadherins, a large family
634 of cell-adhesion molecules that often function as cellular fingerprints to define self from non-self⁵¹.
635 Indeed, interference with Protocadherin 8 (*pcdh8*) produced a subtle yet persistent effect and in this
636 condition some HCs were retained basally (Figure S5). Thus, it is possible that mechanical properties
637 and protocadherin-mediated adhesion patterns work in concert with the guidance cues unraveled here
638 to ensure robust and precise HC positioning. Further studies are needed to dissect the relative
639 contributions of these mechanisms between retinal neurons to expose the comprehensive mechanisms
640 involved in correct retinal layering.

641

642 The two extrinsic, secreted cues that steer HC migration Slit1b/2, binding to Robo2 and
643 Neurturin/Neurturin-like, most likely functioning via Gfr α 1/Ret complex⁸⁷ are, to our knowledge, the
644 first guidance cues reported that influence multipolar migratory neurons. Slit1b/2 with Robo2 act as a
645 repulsive axis that is sufficient make the HCs leave the AC layer. While several Slit-Robo interactions
646 have been studied in neurodevelopment, particularly during axon guidance⁸⁸, these molecules have not
647 yet been shown to be involved in guiding neuronal lamination in vivo. Uncovering this new role for this
648 signaling pair was made possible due to our combination of NATMI analysis and in vivo CRISPR
649 screen. This showed that both, AC-expressed Slit1b/2 and Robo2 on HC membrane, are required for
650 HCs to efficiently depart from the AC layer. Further, the fact that Robo2 protein localizes to the long
651 actin-rich protrusions that HCs extend, hints that protrusions in multipolar migration could be used to
652 enhance the spatial sampling of navigational cues akin to what has been shown for axonal growth
653 cones². In addition to the NATMI analysis for HC guidance principles, the transcriptomics dataset
654 generated here has future potential to elucidate HC, AC, and photoreceptor biology across the retina
655 development.

656 Beyond their Slit-dependent role described here, Robos have also been implicated in Slit-independent
657 functions during tangential migration⁸⁹. Our findings therefore add to the expanding repertoire of Robo-
658 mediated processes in neurodevelopment, and demonstrate for the first time a direct Slit-Robo
659 interaction guiding neuronal migration in vivo⁹⁰. Generally, Slits and Robos have numerous, sometimes
660 independent roles in developing central nervous system, including the retina. For instance, Slits secreted
661 by ACs guide both HC migration (this study) and early retinal ganglion cell axon pathfinding⁷⁰. In such
662 contexts, where a single source of ligand regulates multiple developmental processes, it will be
663 important to better understand how the spatial dynamics and signal dissemination of these cues are
664 modulated to orchestrate precise neuronal layering and circuitry in the developing nervous system.

665
666 The initial apical movement of HCs, mediated by Slit-Robo repulsion, is supported by photoreceptor-
667 derived Neurturin attraction. Although seemingly less potent, Neurturin appears to play an important
668 role for final HC positioning. One possibility is that Neurturin has shorter effective range compared to
669 Slits, acting more locally on HCs that are already closer to the photoreceptor layer. Similar to other
670 GDNF family members, Neurturin is a secreted ligand signaling through Gfr α 1/2 receptor and Ret
671 kinase^{87,91}. This ligand receptor pair was previously shown to be involved in promoting neuronal
672 survival but was to date largely unexplored in the context of neuronal migration.

673 We find that while Neurturin cannot fully rescue HC apical migration when the Slit-Robo axis impaired,
674 its presence enhanced the robustness of successful HC navigation, underscoring its contribution as a re-
675 enforcing guidance cue. Interestingly, in line with our findings, also HCs in developing chick as well
676 as in postnatal mouse retinae express Ret and Gfr α 1, but not Gfr α 2^{92,93}. Further, *Neurturin*^{-/-} mice
677 display an abnormal outer plexiform layer with atypical HC axons⁹², indicating that Neurturin may

678 similarly influence HC migration in mouse and other systems. In addition to its potential migratory role,
679 Neurturin might thus also contribute to later synaptic contact formation between HCs and
680 photoreceptors.

681 Taken together, the spatiotemporal interplay of Slit1b/2–Robo2 and Neurturin–Gfra1a signaling
682 highlights how multipolar migration can be efficiently orchestrated through the integration of spatially
683 distinct extrinsic cues. While multipolar migration is inherently robust, its dependency on such guidance
684 signals may constrain its efficiency to shorter distances. However, the combined action of multiple
685 localized cues could extend its effectiveness and thereby allow this mode of migration to operate
686 reliably even within packed tissue environments, such as those found throughout the developing brain.

687
688 During vertebrate retinal development, the lamination process of five retinal layers largely overlap,
689 unlike the sequential inside-out mechanism in the developing mammalian neocortex². This potentially
690 requires a broader spectrum of migration modes including somal translocation in one or two directions
691 as well as multipolar migration that can be uni- or bidirectional. Multipolar migration in addition to
692 being the main module of migration for HCs, most likely also allows other retinal neurons like ACs,
693 retinal ganglion cells²⁶ and photoreceptors to fine tune their positioning amidst their neighbors within
694 the crowded, yet dynamic tissue environment³⁴.

695 Interestingly, also the development of reptile or avian cortex brain areas that like retinal neurons do not
696 follow the inside out lamination pattern that is seen in the neocortex, show a high prevalence of
697 multipolar migration^{16,18}. This argues that whereas contact-mediated bipolar migratory modes are likely
698 important to enable inside-out type layering, multipolar migration can enhance the robustness of neural
699 tissue patterning through a greater freedom of movement and spatial adaptability. This larger spectrum
700 of possible paths is most likely controlled by the spatiotemporal orchestration of guidance cues, in
701 addition to further chemical and mechanical positional signals, and thereby achieves coordinated
702 patterning. Future comparative studies on how other cells featuring multipolar migration, including
703 other neurons, but also astrocytes, immune- and cancer cells⁹⁴⁻⁹⁶, detect and interpret cell-and tissue
704 level cues to find their target sites, are needed to properly understand the spectrum of possibilities of
705 multipolar migration in development, homeostasis and disease.

706

707

708 **Methods**

709

710 **Zebrafish husbandry**

711 Wild-type (*Danio rerio*; AB and TL strains) and transgenic reporter lines were maintained and bred at
712 28 °C (pH 7.0, conductivity 1000 µS/cm, 14-hour light - 10-hour dark cycle; Techniplast). Embryos for
713 experiments were raised at 28.5 °C or 32 °C in E3 medium. Staging of embryos aged between 38 and
714 120 hours post fertilization (hpf) was conducted according to Kimmel et al⁹⁷. For embryos used in

715 experimental setups, 0.2 mM 1-phenyl-2-thiourea (PTU) (10107703, Acros Organics) in E3 medium
716 was applied to prevent pigmentation. For live-cell imaging and retina dissection, embryos were
717 anesthetized with 0.04% tricaine methane sulfonate (MS-222) (1004671, Pharmaq) in E3 medium. All
718 zebrafish-related work was conducted under the licensing from the DGAV (Directorate-General for
719 Food and Veterinary, Portugal) and in accordance with the European Union directive 2010/63/EU and
720 with the Portuguese Decree Law nº 113/2013.

721

722 **Zebrafish transgenic lines**

723 A triple transgenic line containing *Tg(crx:gap-CFP)*, *Tg(ptfla:Gal4/UAS:gap-YFP)* and *Tg(atoh7:gap-*
724 *RFP)*, transgenes was used to visualize all the retinal neurons⁹⁸. *Tg(atoh7:gap-RFP)* was mated with
725 *Tg(lhx1:GFP)*⁹⁹ to detect photoreceptors and HCs, respectively. *Tg(ptfla:Gal4/UAS:gap-YFP)* labeling
726 retinal interneurons (ACs and HCs) were also used independently. To specifically visualize HCs and
727 ACs, the two transgenes *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* and *Tg(ptfla:DsRed)*¹⁰⁰ were used together or separately.
728 *Tg(vsx1:GFP)*¹⁰¹ was used together with the *Tg(ptfla:DsRed)* to label the bipolar cells and retinal
729 interneurons (ACs and HCs), respectively.

730

731 **DNA constructs and cloning**

732 To construct the Tol2-UAS:Robo2-mCherry expression plasmid, Zebrafish Robo2 CDS, obtained from
733 pCS2-Robo2¹⁰² (a kind gift from E. Goh), was Gateway-cloned into pDONR221 to create
734 pENTR(L1L2)-Robo2. This construct was then combined with pENTR(L4R1)-UAS, pENTR(R2L3)-
735 mCherry and pDEST(R4R3)-Tol2pA2 (originally from Chi-Bin Chien Lab), in a multisite Gateway LR
736 reaction to generate the Tol2-UAS:Robo2-mCherry. pDEST-ptfla:Gal4 was a gift from J.Kaslin and
737 UAS:ActinCB-TagGFP2¹⁰³ (ChromoTek), gifted by P.Panza.

738

739 **DNA and morpholino injections of zebrafish embryos**

740 For mosaic labeling of cells, purified plasmid DNA (Tol2-UAS:Robo2-mCherry or pDEST-ptfla:Gal4
741 with UAS:ActinCB-TagGFP2) were diluted to 25 ng/μl in sterile ddH₂O containing 0.05 % phenol red
742 (P3532, Merck), and 0.5-1 nanoliter of the solution was injected to the cell of one-cell stage
743 *Tg(ptfla:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP)* or wild-type embryos, respectively.

744 All morpholinos (MO) were obtained from Gene Tools, LLC, and injected to the yolk of the one-cell
745 stage embryos. To deplete ACs & HCs, two ptfla translation-blocking morpholinos, 5 ng each, (5'-
746 CCAACACAGTGTCCATTTTTTGTGC-3')⁴³ and (5'-TTGCCAGTAACAACAATCGCCTAC-
747 3')⁴³ were injected together. Robo2 was targeted with 5ng of splice-blocking MO (5'-
748 GTAGCGCAACTCACCATCACTTGG-3')⁷⁷. For Neurturin depletion, 5 ng of Neurturin (5'-
749 TGGCAGCAAACCTCCATAACTTCAT-3') and 5ng of Neurturin-like (5'-
750 CATACCCTCATCTTAGAGCAGCGTG-3'), translation blocking MOs were jointly injected. All

751 injections additionally contained 2ng of p53 MO (5'-GCGCCATTGCTTTGCAAGAATTG-3')¹⁰⁴ to
752 reduce potential apoptosis.

753

754 **Whole-mount immunofluorescence staining of zebrafish embryos**

755 All immunostainings were performed on embryos fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (043368.9M,
756 Thermo Fisher) in 1x PBS, either 3 hours at room temperature (RT) or overnight at 4 °C. After fixation,
757 embryos were washed 4 x 15 minutes (min) with 0.5 % Triton-X in PBS (PBS-T) followed by tissue
758 permeabilization with 0.25% Trypsin-EDTA (10 min for 38 hpf, 15 min for 48-58 hpf, and 18 min for
759 72-120 hpf) on ice. Embryos were then rinsed 4x with PBS-T and blocked with 10 % goat serum in
760 PBS-T either overnight at 4 °C or 3 hours at RT.

761 Following primary antibodies, incubated for 72 hours at 4 °C, were used in the study 1:200 GFP (50430-
762 2-AP, Proteintech), 1:800 HuC/D (A-21271 Invitrogen) 1:500 Zpr-1 (AB_10013803, Zirc), 1:800
763 Prox1 (AB5475, Sigma Aldrich), 1:50 Robo2 (45568, Cell Signaling, 90 % epitope identity to zebrafish
764 Robo2). All primary antibodies were diluted in 1 % goat serum in PBS-T. Primary antibody incubation
765 was followed by 5x 30 min washes with PBS-T and 48-hour incubation at 4 °C with Alexa Fluor 488
766 goat anti-rabbit (A-11034, Invitrogen), Alexa Fluor 647 goat anti-rabbit (A-21245, Invitrogen) or Alexa
767 Fluor 647 goat anti-mouse (A-21236, Invitrogen). Additionally, 2 µg/ml DAPI (MBD0015, Sigma
768 Aldrich) or Alexa Fluor 647 Phalloidin (8940, Cell Signaling) was added to stain the nuclei and F-actin,
769 respectively. Finally, embryos were washed 4 x 15 mins with PBS-T, twice with PBS, and stored in
770 PBS at 4 °C protected from light, until imaging.

771

772 **Retinae dissection and flow cytometry-based sorting of photoreceptor- amacrine- and horizontal** 773 **cells**

774 *Tg(lhx1:GFP); Tg(ptfla:DsRed)* embryos, staged at 38, 48 and 58 hpf, were dechorionated,
775 anesthetized with 0.04 % MS-222 and then placed on a polymethylsiloxane (Sylgard 184, 761036,
776 Merck) -coated dish with ice-cold PBS supplemented with 0.04 % MS-222 and 4 mM EDTA
777 (1084180100, Merck). The retinae were dissected and both lens and the retinal pigment epithelium were
778 removed. Four biological replicates at each developmental stage were performed. 40-50 retinae were
779 collected into a sterile Eppendorf. For each biological replicate, retinal cells were dissociated by
780 removing the PBS-EDTA and incubating them for 10 mins at 28 °C, 350 rpm, with 1x TrypLE Express
781 (12604013, Thermo Fisher), enhancing the dissociation by mechanical pipetting every 5 mins during
782 the incubation. The samples with dissociated retinal cells were then washed twice with ice-cold 1x
783 RNase-free PBS (AM9625, Invitrogen), and filtered through a 100 µm nylon mesh for FACS sorting.
784 photoreceptors (GFP positive), ACs (DsRed positive) and HCs (GFP and DsRed double positive), were
785 sorted according to their fluorescent reporter expression, with FACSAria IIu (100 µm nozzle, BD),
786 collecting 300-500 cells of each cell type straight into respective tubes containing RLT Plus lysis buffer

787 (1053393, Qiagen), snap frozen and stored at -80°C until RNA extraction. The same procedure was
788 conducted for each three developmental stage and for each four biological replicates.

789

790 **RNA sequencing and data processing**

791 The polyA(+) mRNA was isolated from the snap-frozen photoreceptor, HC and AC samples using a
792 oligo-dT capture, followed by reverse-transcription to cDNA and PCR-amplification as in¹⁰⁵. The
793 cDNA quality was confirmed with Fragment Analyzer (Advanced Analytical) and one biological
794 replicate from 48 hpf photoreceptor samples was discarded due to low quality The library preparation
795 for next generation sequencing (NGS) was conducted by carrying out Nextera tagmentation (Illumina)
796 as in¹⁰⁶. The RNA-sequencing was carried out according to Smart-seq2¹⁰⁷ using both NextSeq500 and
797 NextSeq2000 systems (Illumina). The sequencing data is accessible at European Nucleotide Archive
798 under project PRJEB80557. The RNA-seq datasets were aligned to the zebrafish reference genome
799 GRCz11 with STAR (v2.7.0). Gene expression levels were quantified with Subread featureCounts¹⁰⁸.
800 For downstream analysis, the count matrix was normalized and transformed using the DESeq2¹⁰⁹
801 (v1.44) in R (v4.4.1). Differential expression (DE) significance was evaluated by p-value < 0.05 and a
802 \log_2 fold change > 1 , with variance-stabilizing transformation (VST). Visualization of the DE genes
803 was performed using the ggplot2 (v3.5.1) and ggrepel (v0.9.6).

804

805 **NATMI Analysis**

806 Network Analysis Toolkit for Multicellular Interactions (NATMI)⁵² was downloaded from the Github
807 (github.com/forrest-lab/NATMI/) repository. Next, zebrafish connectomeDB (Data file S2) was
808 constructed together with the authors of the original NATMI paper⁵². Shortly, zebrafish ortholog genes
809 were obtained by manual merging of the NCBI homologue database file with Zebrafish Information
810 Network (ZFIN), Human and Zebrafish Orthology file (human_orthos_2022.05.15.txt). The merged
811 zebrafish ortholog data was then cross correlated with human connectomeDB2020
812 (<https://asrhou.github.io/NATMI/>), removing zebrafish genes with no orthologs. The DESeq2-
813 transformed transcriptomic data were preprocessed, and gene expression matrices and cell annotation
814 files were generated following the NATMI GitHub repository. NATMI predicted directional, weighted
815 cell communication networks based on the expression levels of ligands and their corresponding
816 receptors in each cell type (photoreceptor, AC and HC) (Data file S3). Specificity weights were used to
817 identify the most specific cell-cell interactions, which were then quantified for further analysis. The
818 resulting communication networks were visualized using heat maps created with the
819 pheatmap(v1.0.12) package in R (v4.4.1).

820

821 **Blastomere transplantation of Ptf1a depleted embryos**

822 Recipient embryos *Tg(lhx1:GFP)*, injected at one-cell stage with ptf1a MOs, as well as donors
823 *Tg(lhx1:GFP); Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* were dechorionated at 256-cell stage on a glass dish using 2 mg/ml

824 Pronase (P8811, Sigma-Aldrich), followed by 3x rinse with Danieau buffer (0.7 mM KCl, 58 mM,
825 NaCl, 0.6 mM Ca(NO₃)₂, 0.4 mM MgSo₄.7H₂O and 5mM HEPES). Recipients were then transferred
826 onto 1 % agarose mold containing 6 x 25 wells to hold embryos. At mid-blastula stage, 10-100 cells
827 from donor embryos were transplanted into the recipient embryos using a micromanipulator equipped
828 with a 0.1 mm diameter glass needle and an Olympus SZX10 stereo microscope. Transplanted embryos
829 were allowed to recover for 2 hours at 32 °C, prior moving them onto agarose-coated dishes with
830 antibiotics (100 U of penicillin and streptomycin, Thermo Fisher) supplemented E3 at 28.5 °C and
831 growing them in E3 with 0.2 mM PTU until 48 hpf (for live-imaging) or 72 hpf (fixed analysis).

832

833 **In vivo F0 CRISPR guide RNA design and screen**

834 The guide RNA (gRNA) design for each targeted gene used in this study was based on³⁷ and associated
835 protocol (dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.81wgb6r5qlpk/v1). Shortly, CHOPCHOP¹¹⁰ was used to
836 select three crRNAs targeting early asymmetrical exons when possible with highest (> 80%) predicted
837 frameshift mutation frequency¹¹¹ and potential off-targets having over three nucleotide mismatches. The
838 selected crRNAs were further screened to exclude candidates with potential single nucleotide
839 polymorphisms (SNPs)¹¹². The list of crRNAs used in this study are available in Data file S5. All
840 designed crRNAs (2 nmol each), Alt-R™ CRISPR-Cas9 tracrRNA (1072533), Alt-R™ S.p. Cas9
841 Nuclease V3 (1081058) and Duplex buffer (11-01-03-01) were ordered from IDT.

842 To perform the F0 CRISPR screen, the selected three crRNAs per target gene were complexed with
843 tracrRNA and Cas9, respectively, pooled and injected into the yolk of early 1-cell stage *Tg(lhx1:GFP);*
844 *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* embryos as in³⁷. Injected embryos (>200) were grown to 72 hpf in the presence of 0.2
845 mM PTU in E3. Embryos were anesthetized with 0.04 % MS-222 in E3 and placed into 96-well glass-
846 bottom ZF plate (HDK-ZFA101, Funakoshi) enabling uniform larvae alignment. Each well was imaged
847 with a Nikon Eclipse Ti widefield system, equipped with Andor Zyla 4.2 PLUS sCMOS camera and
848 using Plan Apo Lambda D10x objective (Nikon), the TRITC and FITC filter sets and NIS Elements
849 (v5.42) software platform. After imaging, embryos with abnormal (*lhx1:GFP* and *ptf1a:DsRed* positive)
850 HC-cell layer were selected for further analysis. The selected embryos were fixed overnight at 4 °C
851 with 4 % PFA and processed for whole-mount immunofluorescence staining as described above.

852

853 **Robo2 F1 line generation and gDNA sequencing.**

854 The *Tg(lhx1:GFP); Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* embryos were injected with three crRNAs targeting asymmetrical
855 exons 5, 6 and 9 of *Robo2* as described above. Embryos were grown to 72 hpf and screened, selecting
856 embryos with ectopically placed HCs in the AC layer. These embryos, without any additional visible
857 defects, were grown to 3 months of age, after which caudal fin clipping was performed to ten F0
858 founders anesthetized with 0.02 % MS-222. The clipped fins were incubated in a lysis buffer (50 mM
859 Tris-HCl pH 8.5, 1 mM EDTA, 0.5 % Tween-20, 200 µg/mL Proteinase K) for 2 hours at 55 °C and
860 after for 10 mins at 95 °C, to isolate the gDNA.

861 CHOPCHOP¹¹⁰-suggested primers (Data file S5) with overhang adapters (MiSeq system, Illumina),
862 were then used to PCR amplify 200 bp area around each gRNA binding site from the gDNA of each F0
863 founder. After validating the correct amplicon size with agarose gel electrophoresis, the three amplicons
864 were pooled together and sequenced with Illumina Miseq. The resulting sequencing data was aligned
865 to the Zebrafish genome (GRCz11) and visualized with Integrative Genomics Viewer¹¹³ (ver. 2.17.3).
866 Four F0 fish (two males, two females) with frameshift mutations in exon 5 and / or exon 6, leading to
867 early stop codon (Data file S5) were grown and served as founders. All F1 embryos, grown from incross
868 of the F0 founders, phenocopied the HCs ectopic location in the AC layer.

869

870 **Expansion microscopy of the whole zebrafish larvae**

871 *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* or *Tg(ptfla:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP)* embryos grown to 52- and 54 hpf in the presence of
872 0.2 mM PTU, were fixed overnight at 4 °C with 4 % PFA and expanded using an adapted UltraExM
873 protocol based on^{78,114-116}. Prior expansion, the *Tg(ptfla:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP)* embryos were stained
874 with 1:200 GFP (50430-2-AP, Proteintech) whereas the *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* embryos were processed straight
875 for expansion. The embryos were washed 3 x 15 mins with PBS-T and incubated overnight at RT in
876 linking solution (0.1 mg/mL acryloyl X-SE (Invitrogen, A20770) in 0.1 % PBS-T). Monomer solution
877 (38 % w/v sodium acrylate (408220, Sigma Aldrich) 40 % w/v acrylamide (A9099, Sigma Aldrich), 2
878 % w/v N,N'-Methylenebisacrylamide (274135, Sigma Aldrich), all in ddH₂O) was applied to the
879 samples, containing 1:40 546nm-Actin ExM (Chrometra) and 2 µg/ml DAPI (MBD0015, Sigma
880 Aldrich) for F-actin and nuclei labeling. Embryos were incubated for 24 hours in the dark, at RT.

881 For gelation, embryos were placed on pre-cooled gelation chambers onto which ice-cold monomer
882 solution with 0.5 % TEMED (1.10732, Sigma Aldrich) and 0.5 % APS (9592.3, Roth) was added.
883 Embryos were quickly aligned with the retina facing to the bottom of the gelation chamber and a
884 coverslip was inverted on the top. Gelation proceeded for 10 minutes on ice, followed by incubation for
885 3 hours at 37 °C or 24 hours at RT in the dark in a humidified chamber. Following gelation, A digestion
886 buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 1 mM EDTA pH 8.0, 0.5 % Triton X-100, 0.8 M Guanidine HCl) and
887 8 U/ml Proteinase K (New England Biolabs P8107S) in ddH₂O) were added and gels were incubated at
888 RT for 16 hours. After digestion, gels were transferred to ddH₂O to initiate expansion. The water was
889 changed twice after 30 minutes, followed by overnight incubation at RT to allow for complete
890 expansion. The expanded gels were cut to separate the expanded zebrafish heads, and these samples
891 were immobilized with retina facing down onto 0.1 mg/ml poly-D-lysine (A3890401, Thermo Fisher)
892 -coated glass coverslips. The samples were imaged in ddH₂O using a LSM 980 point-scanning confocal
893 with Airyscan 2 Multiplex (Zeiss), operated in Airyscan SR mode through microscopy ZEN Blue v 3.3
894 (Zeiss) software and using LD-C Apochromat 40x/1.1 W Corr M27 water-immersion objective (Zeiss).
895 Airyscan 3D-processing was then conducted with auto filters in ZEN Blue v3.3 (Zeiss).

896

897 **In situ hybridization of whole mount embryos and retinal sections**

898 Oligos to generate probes for detecting Slit2 mRNA as previously used in⁷⁰ were utilized, containing
899 T7 promoter site for the Slit2 sense: 5'-TAATACGACTCACTATAGGCAACAGAGAATCCTTCCT
900 GC-3' and SP6 promoter site in the anti-sense 5'-ATTTAGGTGACACTATAGATGCGTCTGATAG
901 TGATCTCG -3' were used to amplify 897 bp segment corresponding to Slit2 3'-region. Similarly
902 Robo2 sense 5'-TAATACGACTCACTATAGGTGTACAGGCAGATGTCAGGC-3' and anti-sense
903 5'-ATTTAGGTGACACTATAGATCCTCCTCCAGTAGAGCCAG-3' oligos documented in¹¹⁷ and
904 including additional T7 and SP6 sites, respectively, were used to amplify 642 bp segment corresponding
905 to Robo2 3'-region. Using the PCR-amplified DNA as templates, the DIG-labeled mRNA probes were
906 generated using the DIG RNA Labeling Kit (SP6/T7) (11175025910, Roche) and purified with Pure
907 Link RNA Mini Kit (12183018A, Invitrogen). The dot blot assay using serial dilutions of each DIG-
908 labeled probe, was conducted on a Hybond-N+ (Amersham) membrane and detected with 0.08 mg/ml
909 nitro-blue tetrazolium (NBT) (11383213001, Roche) and 0.1 mg/ml 5-bromo-4-chloro-3'-
910 indolyphosphate (BCIP) (11383221001, Roche) confirming the optimal labeling of each probe.

911
912 Zebrafish embryos at 38, 48 and 58 hpf, fixed overnight at 4 °C with 4 % PFA were dehydrated and
913 kept in 100 % methanol for 48 hours. The embryos were gradually rehydrated, treated with 10 µg/ml
914 Proteinase K (EO0491, Thermo Fisher) for 30 minutes at RT, and acetylated following the published
915 protocols^{118,119}. Each probe was added to the overnight pre-hybridized (65 °C) embryos at 0.2 ng/µl in
916 hybridization buffer and incubated for 24h at 65 °C. Hybridization buffer was used as reported in¹¹⁸,
917 except that it additionally included 50% de-ionized formamide (F9037, Sigma Aldrich). The wash
918 buffers I-III further contained 25 %, 12,5 % and 0 % of the de-ionized formamide, respectively.
919 Following the hybridization, embryos were washed, blocked and the colorimetric signal detection was
920 performed as in¹¹⁸. In brief, for colorimetric signal detection 1:2000 dilution of anti-DIG-AP
921 (11093274910, Roche) was applied overnight at 4 °C, followed by washes and color development with
922 0.08 mg/ml NBT, 0.1 mg/ml BCIP in RT, protected from light. Part of the embryos of each
923 developmental stage that were probed for both Slit2 and Robo2, were embedded overnight at 4°C in 30
924 % sucrose-PBS, transferred to O.C.T (4583, Sakura) and cryosectioned with Cryostat 3050S (Leica) to
925 20 µm sections. Both, the whole-mount and sectioned hybridized embryos were imaged using a Zeiss
926 Stereo Lumar.V12 stereo microscope, equipped with UI-3370CP Rev. 2 (Imaging Development
927 Systems, IDS) color camera operated with uEye (IDS).

928

929 **Spinning disk live-imaging of zebrafish embryos**

930 To perform live-imaging of HC migration in controls or upon perturbations (MOs or KOs), between 5
931 and 20 embryos, anesthetized with 0.04 % MS-222, were embedded into 0.7 % low-melting agarose
932 (A9045, Sigma Aldrich) in E3 medium. Either glass-bottom 35mm dishes (P35G-1.5-14-C, MatTek)
933 or 2-well glass-bottom µ-slides (80286, Ibidi) were used for embedding. 15 min post embedding, when
934 the agarose was solidified, the dish was filled with 32 °C E3 medium containing 0.2 mM PTU and 0.04

935 % MS-222. Imaging was conducted at 32 °C using Marianas SDC (Intelligent Imaging Innovations, 3I)
936 spinning disk confocal, operated through Nikon Ti2 Eclipse and Slidebook 2024 (3I) software platform
937 and equipped with Yokogawa CSU-W1 scanner plus the Uniformizer (Yokogawa), and Photometrics
938 Prime 95B sCMOS (Teledyne) camera. The imaging dish was allowed to settle to 32 °C for 30 mins
939 prior the onset of acquisition. Z-stacks of 80 µm with 1 µm step size, were acquired every 10-20 mins
940 using 40x CFI Plan Apo Lambda S 40x Sil objective (Nikon). Embryos were imaged for a total of 12
941 to 24 hours, depending on the experimental set up.

942

943 **Airyscan confocal scan of whole-mount zebrafish retinae**

944 Whole-mount, stained embryos between 38-120 hpf, were embedded into 1 % low-melting agarose
945 (A9045, Sigma Aldrich) in E3 medium and their retinae were imaged using a LSM 980 point-scanning
946 confocal with Airyscan 2 Multiplex (Zeiss), using the Airyscan 2 detector and LD-C Apochromat
947 40x/1.1 W Corr M27 water-immersion objective (Zeiss). Acquisition was conducted in SR-8Y
948 multiplex mode, operated through microcopy ZEN Blue v3.3 (Zeiss) software. 50 µm Z-stacks with 1
949 µm step size were acquired that were subsequently Airyscan 3D-processed using the auto filters in ZEN
950 Blue v3.3 (Zeiss).

951

952 **Image processing and analysis**

953 Imaging data was processed using Fiji¹²⁰. Data from live-imaging experiments was processed with 3D
954 median filter (x,y,z; 2.0), cropped and Z-projected (Maximum intensity projection). Visualization of
955 cell tracks for the videos were performed with DrawArrowInMovie-tool¹²¹. Imaris (v10.0.0, Oxford
956 Instruments) was used for 3D-rendering the Z-projections of expanded retinae imaging data. OpenShot
957 Video editor (OpenShot Studios, LLC) was employed to concatenate the videos and add titles. Inkscape
958 (v1.2.3) was used for the figure generation and bioicons (bioicons.com) for drawing illustrations.

959

960 **Quantitative analysis of HCs in the AC-layer in different F0 knockouts**

961 To count HCs in the AC-layer upon introduction of different KOs, HCs were segmented from 72- or 80
962 hpf fixed whole-mount *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* [HCs, photoreceptors]; *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* [HCs, ACs] DAPI-
963 stained KO retinae (20 µm maximum intensity Z-projections), using the GFP signal for cyto3
964 segmentation network in Cellpose v3.0.8¹²². The resulting outline ROIs from segmented cells were then
965 transferred to Fiji with the respective maximum intensity projection and there a 130 x 300 µm area
966 (excluding ciliary marginal zone) from each sample, was analyzed for HC positioning. Prior counting
967 the cells, the ptf1a:DsRed signal was utilized to manually remove any DsRed-negative ROIs
968 (photoreceptors). All the cell ROIs within the 130 x 300 µm area were counted and binned either as
969 laminated (if ≤ 5 µm from photoreceptor layer) or as stuck (>5 µm from the photoreceptor layer). Nuclei
970 staining (DAPI) was used to determine the photoreceptor layer as well as the general retina lamination
971 (Data file S6). Finally, the ratio of stuck to total HCs counted was used in the quantitative analysis.

972

973 **Analysis of HC cytokinesis positions**

974 Divisions occurring in *Tg(lhx1:GFP); Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* embryos injected RNPs targeting either
975 *Scrambled* or *Robo2* and imaged from 48 hpf to 72 hpf, the HC (lhx1:GFP and ptf1a:DsRed positive)
976 were manually located from a set ROI registering the same area in the nasal-temporal retinal axis. The
977 position of mitotic HCs, respective to the basal side of the photoreceptors (lhx1:GFP positive), were
978 manually measured using the Fiji Line tool as in²⁵ (Data file S6). To track the sister HC final positioning,
979 both sister cells from each division event, were manually tracked until the end of lamination (72 hpf)
980 and cross-correlated with the division position.

981

982 **Statistical analysis and reproducibility**

983 All statistical tests were conducted using the GraphPad Prism v9.4.0. All analyzed data was first tested
984 for normality, using Anderson-Darling and Shapiro-Wilk tests. As the analyzed data was not normally
985 distributed across different samples, Mann-Whitney U test was applied for pairwise comparison of
986 independent groups with mixed distributions and smaller sample sizes. Exact p-values and sample sizes
987 are reported in the respective figure legends.

988

989 **Author contributions**

990 Jaakko Lehtimäki: Conceptualization, funding acquisition, data acquisition and curation, methodology,
991 visualization, analysis, writing (original draft). Jingtao Lilue: methodology, data curation and
992 visualization, writing. Mario del Rosario: Conceptualization, methodology, investigation, writing
993 (editing). Elisa Nerli: methodology, data curation. Ricardo Henriques: Conceptualization, writing
994 (editing). Caren Norden: Conceptualization, supervision, project administration, funding acquisition,
995 writing (original draft).

996

997 **Acknowledgements**

998 The authors would like to thank the Cell Biology of Tissue Morphogenesis laboratory, especially João
999 Coelho, Renata Cunha and Ricardo Ribeiro for the help with cloning and Mariana Gil and Margarida
1000 Cruz with the help on transplantation. We further thank the Flow cytometry, Bioimaging, Genomic,
1001 Bioinformatics, Histopathology and Aquatic facilities at the Gulbenkian Institute for Molecular
1002 Medicine (GIMM, formerly Instituto Gulbenkian de Ciencia, IGC) for experimental and technical
1003 support. The authors would further like to acknowledge Rui Hou and Allistair Forest on their help on
1004 updating the NATMI connectome for zebrafish as well as Guillaume Jacquemet and Julien Vermot for
1005 their helpful comments on the manuscript. We would also like to thank Eyleen Goh for providing the
1006 pCS2-Robo2, Jan Kaslin for the pDEST-ptf1a:Gal4 and Paolo Panza for the UAS:ActinCB-TagGFP2
1007 construct. Caren Norden discloses support for the research of this work from European Research
1008 Council (ERC) consolidator grant (H2020 ERC-2018-CoG-81904). Jaakko Lehtimäki was additionally

1009 supported for the research of this work from Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia CEEC
 1010 (2023.07063 .CEECIND/CP2854/CT0002). Ricardo Henriques and Mario Del Rosario were supported
 1011 by the ERC under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant
 1012 agreement No. 101001332) (to R.H.). The authors declare no competing financial interests.
 1013
 1014

1015
 1016 **Figure S1. Additional data on multipolar photoreceptors and HC lamination in control and in *vsx1+vsx2***
 1017 **and *prdm1* knockout embryos.**
 1018 **A)** HCs (cyan and yellow) positioning at 38, 48 and 58 hpf. *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* labels HCs and photoreceptors and
 1019 *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* both ACs and HCs in the retina. After 48 hpf, the GFP expression decreases in photoreceptors.

1020 Nuclei were stained with DAPI (grey). Illustration on the right displays the differential labeling of the three cell
1021 types in the *Tg(lhx1:GFP); Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* embryos. See also Figures 1A and 3A. Scale bars: 20 μm .
1022 **B)** The effectiveness of bipolar cell depletion upon *vsx1+vsx2* KO in F0 embryos was compared to control (i) and
1023 assessed by the absence of *Tg(vsx1:GFP, grey)* signal in KOs (ii) that labels bipolar cells as well as extension of
1024 *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed, yellow)* signal that covers the presumptive bipolar cell layer (areas indicated with dashed line).
1025 Scale bars: 20 μm .
1026 **C)** *prdm1a* knockout retina (72 hpf) displaying a control-like retinal lamination. *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* labels HCs and
1027 photoreceptors and *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* both HCs and ACs. Nuclei were stained with DAPI. Scale bar: 20 μm .
1028 **D)** *prdm1b* knockout retina (80hpf), showing some HCs remaining in the AC layer (marked by white arrows) (see
1029 also Figure 1E). *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* labels HCs and photoreceptors and *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* both HCs and ACs. Nuclei
1030 were stained with DAPI (grey). Scale bars: 20 μm .
1031 **E)** Time series of multipolar photoreceptor *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* apical migration and division in the photoreceptor layer,
1032 (marked by white arrow), observed in the *Ptf1a* MO-treated retina lacking ACs and HCs. Scale bars: 10 μm .
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Figure S2. In vivo CRISPR screen functionality controls and additional NATMI data analysis.

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A) Schematics of guide RNA targeting principles for the in vivo F0 knockout screen. i) Scatter dot plot of *onecut1* expression, showing normalized counts for HC, AC and photoreceptors (PR) at 38 hpf (circle), 48 hpf (triangle) and 58 hpf (square). Mean and SD from four biological replicates are shown for each time point. ii) Three guide RNA-Cas9 complexes (RNPs) targeting early exons (*onecut1* exon illustration from ensembl.org, ENSDART0000010177.6) were pooled and injected into 1-cell stage embryos. iii) Automated imaging of injected embryos in 96-well plate format, screening them at 72 hpf for abnormal HC-cell layer (cyan) formation in the retina. Scale bars: 500 μ m.

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1044 **B)** 72 hpf *scrambled* KO control and *onecut1* KO F0 embryos. Dashed line shows the HC-cell layer. HCs
 1045 *Tg(lhx1:GFP, cyan)*, HCs and ACs *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed, yellow)*, nuclei were stained with DAPI (grey).
 1046 **C)** Volcano plots for HCs, ACs and photoreceptors (PR) comparing transcriptomics at 38 hpf vs. 48 hpf with the
 1047 short-listed ligand-receptor candidates (see Figures 3B and S2D) highlighted. Ligands are shown in magenta and
 1048 receptors in light blue. Thresholds (dashed lines) = \log_2 fold change > 1, $\text{Log}_{10}(\text{P value}) > 1$.
 1049 **D)** Heatmap visualization of the NATMI (Log_2 mean expression weight) data on repulsive cues of Semaphorin-
 1050 class molecules and their cognate receptors. The ligand-receptor candidates with the largest changes in the
 1051 expression weights between the time points are shown in bold.
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1055 **Figure S3. Slit2 and Robo2 mRNA expression in the developing retina and *slit1b/2-robo2* knockouts and**
1056 **Robo2 morpholino phenotypes.**

1057 **A)** Slit2 in situ whole mount (i-iv) and sectioned (v-vi) heads at 38 hpf, 48 hpf and 58 hpf. A Slit2-sense probe
1058 was used as negative control (iv). At 38 hpf Slit2 mRNA is detected in the optic nerve (black arrows). At 48- and
1059 58 hpf, an AC-layer specific signal emerges (white arrows). Scale bars: 100 μm (whole mounts) and 50 μm
1060 (sections).

1061 **B)** Robo2 in situ whole mount (i-iv) and sectioned (v-vi) heads at 38 hpf, 48 hpf and 58 hpf. A Robo2-sense probe
1062 was used as negative control (iv). Robo2 mRNA expression is detected from 48 hpf onwards in the retinal ganglion
1063 cell layer (black arrow) and faintly in the AC layer (white arrow). At 58 hpf the signal is seen at the retinal ganglion
1064 cell layer (black arrow) and within the inner nuclear layer including the HC cell layer (white arrow). Scale bars:
1065 100 μm (whole mounts) and 50 μm (sections).

1066 **C)** Robo2 antibody staining of the 54 hpf retina. Punctate Robo2 signal (white arrows) is observed at the
1067 membrane as well as on the protrusions of the migrating Ptf1a-positive HCs (fire). Dashed lines label the
1068 photoreceptor layer. Scale bars: 5 μm .

1069 **D)** Time-lapse series of Robo2 (fire/white) in a migrating HC. UAS:Robo2-mCherry (fire/white) injected into
1070 *Tg(ptf1a:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP, cyan)* labeling HCs and ACs. Dashed lines illustrate two Robo2-positive ACs and
1071 one HC (white arrow). The white arrow points towards prominent Robo2-positive puncta at the tip of HC
1072 protrusions. Scale bars: 10 μm . See also Video S5 for additional labeling of Robo2 positive foci.

1073 **E)** *scrambled* F0 versus *slit1b+slit2* F0, *robo2* F0 and *robo2* F1 KOs with HCs *Tg(lhx1:GFP, cyan)*, ACs
1074 *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed, yellow)* labelled. Nuclei were stained with DAPI (grey) *robo2* F0 KO was stained with phalloidin
1075 for F-actin (grey), instead of DAPI. Related to Figure 4A. Scale bars: 20 μm .

1076 **F)** Representative *slit2+robo2* F0 KO retinae at 96 hpf. The phenotype is similar to *robo2* KO (Figure S3E).
1077 *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed, yellow)* labels ACs and HCs. *Tg(lhx1:GFP, cyan)* labels the HCs. Nuclei are labeled with DAPI,
1078 grey. Scale bar: 20 μm .

1079 **G)** Retinae of Robo2 splice-blocking morpholino (MO)-injected 72 hpf larvae. *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* labels ACs and
1080 HCs. *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* labels the HCs. Scale bars: 20 μm .

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1084 **Figure S4. Candidate knockouts of attractive candidates in control background, Neurturin morpholino**
 1085 **experiments and 3D-rendered migrating HCs from expansion microscopy data.**

1086 **A)** 3D-surface rendering of HCs expressing cytoplasmic *Tg(lhx1:GFP)* (i) or membrane *Tg(ptf1a:Gal4; UAS:gap-*
 1087 *YFP)* signal (ii) (cyan) in 54 hpf expanded retinae. Nuclei (grey) were rendered using DAPI signal. The basal side
 1088 of the photoreceptor layer is labeled by dashed white lines. Scale bars: 20 µm. See also Video S7.

1089 **B)** Scatter dot plot of a zebrafish Neurturin-like (LOC103910147) gene *FO834855.1 / nrtm-like* expression in
 1090 HCs, ACs and photoreceptors (PR) at 38 hpf (circle), 48 hpf (triangle) and 58 hpf (square). Normalized counts
 1091 from three to four biological replicates (Data file S1) with mean and SD are shown for each time point.
 1092 Upregulation of *nrtm-like* occurs specifically in photoreceptors, similar to *nrtm* (Figure 3B).

1093 **C)** 80 hpf retinae from i) *nrtm+nrtm-like* (Neurturin), ii) *ntf3* (NT-3)-, iii) *gfra1a*- (Neurturin receptor), iv) *ntrk3a*
 1094 (NT-3 receptor) F0 KOs. Related to quantifications shown in Figure 5F. *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed, yellow)* labels ACs and
 1095 HCs, *Tg(lhx1:GFP, cyan)* labels HCs. Nuclei were stained with DAPI (grey). Scale bars: 20 µm.

1096 **D)** 80 hpf retinae from *ntf3* KO in *robo2* F1 background. Related to quantifications shown in Figure 5F. Scale
 1097 bar: 20 µm.

1098 **E)** Neurturin translation-blocking morpholino (targeting both *nrtm+nrtm-like*) injection into the *robo2* F1 KO
 1099 embryos, recapitulates the Neurturin KO phenotype in laminated 80 hpf retinae (see also Figure 5E). HCs

1100 *Tg(lhx1:GFP); Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* in cyan and yellow, ACs *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* in yellow and nuclei (DAPI) in grey.
 1101 Scale bars: 20 μ m.
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 1105 **Figure S5. Additional F0 knockouts targeting HC multipolar migration.**
 1106 The additional F0 knockouts (KO) were selected or manual curation of the transcriptomics data or through in vivo
 1107 screen using NATMI analysis data (see Figures 3B, S2D). The targets include additional ligands and receptors,
 1108 as well as cell-cell contact- and extracellular matrix-related targets. Larvae were fixed at either 72 hpf or 96 hpf.
 1109 The knockouts were split into three categories: 1) No phenotype: retinæ looked similar to the controls; 2) Mild
 1110 phenotype: either delayed retinal lamination, a small number of HCs (cyan) remaining in the AC layer or a slightly
 1111 disrupted retinal morphology based on AC (yellow) and nuclei staining, is observed; 3) Severe phenotype: affects
 1112 general retina morphology and/or development or leads to embryonic death. *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)*, yellow labels ACs
 1113 and HCs. *Tg(lhx1:GFP)*, cyan labels the HCs. Nuclei were stained with DAPI (grey). For *myo10* F0 KO, instead
 1114 of DAPI, F-actin was stained by phalloidin (grey). For the *ret* KO, all the injected embryos were dead by 24 hpf.
 1115 Scale bars: 20 μ m.
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1118 **Video legends**

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1120 **Video S1. Multipolar HC apical migration among other neurons in the developing retina, related**

1121 **to Figure 1B and Figures 5A-C. A)** Example of a multipolar HC (cyan, white arrowhead) leaving the

1122 AC-layer (yellow and cyan) and performing multipolar migration to travel towards and laminate below

1123 the photoreceptor layer (magenta). The bipolar cells are also weakly labelled with cyan. Time interval

1124 20 minutes, Scale bar: 10 μ m. Acquisition started at 48 hours post fertilization (hpf). *Tg(ato7:gap-*

1125 *RFP)* reporter line labels all retinal neurons except bipolar cells; *Tg(ptf1a:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP)*

1126 reporter line labels ACs and HCs and *Tg(crx:gap-CFP)* reporter photoreceptors and the bipolar cells

1127 (lower expression levels). **B)** Two HCs with membrane labeling (cyan arrowheads) leaving the AC-

1128 layer and extending multiple protrusions during their migration. The second HC labeled, moves away

1129 from the Z-plane mid-acquisition. *Tg(ptf1a:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP)* reporter line labels the membranes

1130 of ACs and HCs. Time interval 10 minutes. Scale bar: 10 μ m. Acquisition started at 52 hpf.

1131

1132 **Video S2. Multipolar HC apical migration in the *vsx1+vsx2* KO retina, related to Figures 1D and**

1133 **S1B.** HCs (cyan) successfully leave the AC-layer (also in cyan) and migrate apically in *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed,*

1134 *cyan); Tg(vsx1:GFP, grey)* reporter line embryos where, due to *vsx1+vsx2* KO, *vsx1*-positive bipolar

1135 cells (grey) are absent. The extension of *ptf1a*-positive ACs to presumptive bipolar cell positions is

1136 observed as seen in Figure S1B. Time interval 10 minutes. Scale bar: 10 μ m. Acquisition started at 48

1137 hpf.

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1139 **Video S3. Multipolar HC apical migration in the *prdm1b* KO retina, related to Figures 1E and**

1140 **S1D.** HCs labelled by *Tg(lhx1:GFP, fire)* reporter, migrating to ectopic apical positions (white

1141 arrowheads) within the presumptive photoreceptor layer, labelled by *Tg(ato7:gap-RFP, grey)* reporter

1142 looks abnormal due to *prdm1b* KO. *Tg(ato7:gap-RFP)* reporter labels all retinal neurons except

1143 bipolar cells. In areas with more intact photoreceptor layer, HCs (cyan arrowhead), laminate beneath it

1144 as seen in controls. Time interval 10 minutes. Scale bar: 10 μ m. Acquisition started at 50 hpf.

1145

1146 **Video S4. Donor HC apical migration in control and in *Ptf1a* MO retina, related to Figures 2D-**

1147 **E.**

1148 **A)** Lamination of HCs in the developing control donor retina. White arrowhead indicates migration and

1149 lamination of a HC below the photoreceptor layer as shown in Figure 2D. The white box labels the

1150 region from which the time-lapse images were extracted in Figure 2D. *Tg(lhx1:GFP, cyan)* reporter

1151 line labels photoreceptors and HCs and *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed)* ACs and HCs. Time interval 15 minutes. Scale

1152 bar: 20 μ m. Acquisition started at 48 hpf. **B)** Migration of control donor HCs in the developing retina

1153 depleted of ACs. White and grey arrowheads label two HCs in the AC-layer unable to initiate the apical

1154 multipolar migration. *Tg(lhx1:GFP, cyan)* reporter labels early photoreceptors and HCs and

1155 *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed, yellow)* reporter ACs and HCs. Time interval 15 minutes. Scale bar: 10 μ m.
1156 Acquisition started at 48 hpf.

1157

1158 **Video S5. Robo2 localization dynamics in an HC initiating apical migration, related to Figure**
1159 **S3D.** Injected UAS:Robo2-mCherry (fire) into *Tg(ptf1a:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP, cyan)* reporter line
1160 embryos, labeling two ACs and one HC in the developing retina. The arrowheads point towards Robo2-
1161 positive foci in protrusions dynamically appearing and disappearing around the migrating HC. Time
1162 interval 10 minutes. Scale bar: 10 μ m. Acquisition started at 38 hpf.

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1164 **Video S6. Multipolar HC migration in scrambled KO and in *slit2+robo2* F0 KO embryos, related**
1165 **to Figures 4D-E. A)** HC migration in the *scrambled* KO retina. White arrowheads follow apical
1166 migration and division below the photoreceptor layer of one HC. Time interval 15 minutes. Scale bar:
1167 10 μ m. Acquisition started at 48 hpf. **B)** White and grey arrowheads follow two HCs migrating in
1168 *slit2+robo2* KO retina. These two HCs divide into two sister HCs that are further tracked with the same
1169 type of arrowheads. Time interval 15 minutes. Scale bar: 10 μ m. Acquisition started at 48 hpf. For both
1170 A-B *Tg(lhx1:GFP, cyan)* reporter labels HCs and *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed, yellow)* reporter ACs and HCs.

1171

1172 **Video S7. 3D-rendered HC protrusions in a retina subjected to expansion microscopy, related to**
1173 **Figures 5C and S4A.** 3D-surface rendering of HCs in *Tg(ptf1a:Gal4; UAS:gap-YFP, cyan)* reporter
1174 line and nuclei (DAPI, grey) in 52 hpf retina as HCs migrate apically towards the photoreceptors. First
1175 frames display the non-3D-rendered signal for both HCs and nuclei. Scale bar: 3-10 μ m, depending on
1176 the zoom-in.

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1178 **Video S8. Multipolar HC migration upon *nrtin+nrtin-like* F0 KO in *robo2* F1 background, related**
1179 **to Figure 5E.** HCs migration (cyan and yellow) in developing retina depleted of Neurturin (*nrtin+nrtin-*
1180 *like* KO) and of Robo2 (*robo2* F1). Acquisition started at 50 hpf where in control retina (see Video 4),
1181 HCs initiate apical migration. *Tg(lhx1:GFP, cyan)* reporter labels HCs and *Tg(ptf1a:DsRed, yellow)*
1182 reporter ACs and HCs. Time interval 10 minutes. Scale bar: 20 μ m. Acquisition started at 50 hpf.

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